

22IEM06 S-CALe Up

D7

Validation of the predictable spectral response of photodiodes over the extended ranges between 200 nm and 400 nm and 850 nm to 1050 nm with an uncertainty better than 0.2%.

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable: PTB

Due date of the deliverable: March 2026

Actual submission date of the deliverable: June 2026

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EURAMET. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

Glossary

EQE	External quantum efficiency
EQD	External quantum deficiency
IQD	Internal quantum deficiency
PQED	Predictable quantum efficient detector
CESR	Cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer

1 Summary

This deliverable reports on the validation of the prediction of the spectral responsivity $s(\lambda)$ of photodiodes over the extended wavelength ranges between 200 nm and 400 nm and 850 nm to 1050 nm with an uncertainty better than 0.2 %.

Photodiodes manufactured in the 18SIB10 chipS-CALe project were studied in the wavelength range from 300 nm to 400 nm and from 850 nm to about 1030 nm. Photodiodes manufactured in this project were studied in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 400 nm.

The spectral responsivity was predicted for a radiation trap detector arrangement comprising two or more induced-junction photodiodes. This leads to the incident radiation being reflected several times between the photodiodes, resulting in a drastic reduction in reflectance compared to a single photodiode.

The prediction of the spectral responsivity is based on the ideal photodiode where one incident photon creates one electron in the outside circuitry of the photodiode. The spectral responsivity of the ideal photodiode is

$$s_{ideal}(\lambda) = \frac{e\lambda}{hc} \quad (1)$$

which can be expressed in terms of the vacuum wavelength of the incident radiation λ , the elementary charge e , Planck constant h , and the speed of light in vacuum c .

The deviations of the spectral responsivity of a non-ideal photodiode or of a radiation trap detector arrangement of non-ideal photodiodes from the ideal case are described by the following quantities:

- the spectrally dependent reflection loss $\rho(\lambda)$, caused by the reflectance of the front side of a photodiode or of the entire radiation trap detector arrangement,
- the spectrally dependent internal quantum deficiency (IQD) $\delta(\lambda)$, which corresponds to charge-carrier recombination losses,
- the spectrally dependent reflection loss $\alpha(\lambda)$ of long-wavelength radiation that penetrates the photodiode and is partly reflected by the aluminium layer on the rear surface, and partly absorbed by this aluminium layer, and
- the spectrally dependent quantum yield $\gamma(\lambda)$, which describes the number of created electron-hole pairs per absorbed photon.

The spectral responsivity of the radiation trap detector arrangement of non-ideal photodiode, which is called Predictable Quantum Efficient Detector (PQED) in this project, is

$$s(\lambda) = \frac{e\lambda}{hc} (1 - \rho(\lambda))(1 - \delta(\lambda))(1 - \alpha(\lambda))\gamma(\lambda) \quad (2)$$

This project thoroughly studied the quantities $\rho(\lambda)$, $\delta(\lambda)$, $\alpha(\lambda)$, $\gamma(\lambda)$ in order to predict the spectral responsivity of the PQED with low uncertainty. In addition, the predicted spectral responsivity was validated by comparing it with the measured spectral responsivity, which is based on calibrations against the established primary detector standard for optical radiant power, the Cryogenic Electrical Substitution Radiometer (CESR). Due to the extent and complexity of these studies and validation measurements, this work is not described by one paper but by several papers which are listed in the 'Attachments' section.

It is worth noticing the following spectral limitations:

- The quantum yield is equal to 1 for wavelengths longer than about 550 nm and can be larger than 1 only for shorter wavelengths.
- The reflection loss $\alpha(\lambda)$ cannot be larger than the part of the incident radiation that penetrates the photodiode with a thickness of about 500 μm and reaches the rear surface. This part is about 100 ppm of the radiation passing the front surface of the photodiode for a wavelength of 940 nm and even smaller for shorter wavelengths. Thus, $\alpha(\lambda)$ is relevant only for wavelengths longer than 940 nm and can be neglected otherwise.

Consequently, equation (2) can be simplified depending on the wavelength range:

$$s(\lambda) = \frac{e\lambda}{hc} (1 - \rho(\lambda))(1 - \delta(\lambda))y(\lambda), \quad \text{for } \lambda < 550 \text{ nm} \quad (3a)$$

$$s(\lambda) = \frac{e\lambda}{hc} (1 - \rho(\lambda))(1 - \delta(\lambda)), \quad \text{for } 550 \text{ nm} \leq \lambda < 840 \text{ nm} \quad (3b)$$

$$s(\lambda) = \frac{e\lambda}{hc} (1 - \rho(\lambda))(1 - \delta(\lambda))(1 - \alpha(\lambda)), \quad \text{for } 840 \text{ nm} \leq \lambda \quad (3c)$$

It is sometimes convenient to discuss the external quantum efficiency (EQE)

$$q(\lambda) = s(\lambda) / \left(\frac{e\lambda}{hc}\right) = (1 - \rho(\lambda))(1 - \delta(\lambda))(1 - \alpha(\lambda))y(\lambda) \quad (4)$$

or the external quantum deficiency (EQD)

$$\Delta(\lambda) = 1 - q(\lambda) \quad (5)$$

The external quantum efficiency and the external quantum deficiency can be calculated also $s_{meas}(\lambda)$ responsivity $s_{meas}(\lambda)$ according to

$$q_{meas}(\lambda) = s_{meas}(\lambda) / \left(\frac{e\lambda}{hc}\right), \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta_{meas}(\lambda) = 1 - s_{meas}(\lambda) / \left(\frac{e\lambda}{hc}\right), \quad (7)$$

If the losses are small compared to 1 ($\rho(\lambda), \delta(\lambda), \alpha(\lambda) \ll 1$), eq. (4) can be simplified to

$$q(\lambda) = (1 - \rho(\lambda) - \delta(\lambda) - \alpha(\lambda))y(\lambda), \quad \text{for } \rho(\lambda), \delta(\lambda), \alpha(\lambda) \ll 1 \quad (8)$$

In the wavelength range $\lambda > 550$ nm, where $y(\lambda) \equiv 1$, eq. (5) can be further simplified to

$$\Delta(\lambda) = \rho(\lambda) + \delta(\lambda) + \alpha(\lambda), \quad \text{for } y(\lambda) \equiv 1 \text{ and } \rho(\lambda), \delta(\lambda), \alpha(\lambda) \ll 1 \quad (9)$$

Paper 1 describes the prediction of the IQD of a PQED over the spectral range from 200 nm to 1100 nm, using a 3D charge carrier transport simulation model fitted to measured photocurrent-voltage data. The PQED is based on SiO₂/SiN_x passivated induced-junction photodiodes. To validate the predicted IQD, the measured and the predicted EQD are compared. The measured EQD $\Delta_{meas}(\lambda)$ is calculated according to eq. (7) from the spectral responsivity measured against the CESR. The predicted EQD is according to eq. (9)

$$\Delta_{pred}(\lambda) \approx \delta_{pred}(\lambda), \quad (10)$$

since $\rho(\lambda) \leq 10$ ppm for p-polarised radiation in the wavelength range from 400 nm to 1000 nm and the PQEDs discussed there. This is valid as long as it can be assumed that $\alpha(\lambda) \approx 0$, which is the case at least for $\lambda \leq 840$ nm.

Figure 3 of **Paper 1** shows a very good agreement of the measured EQD $\Delta_{meas}(\lambda)$ and the predicted IQD within the uncertainty of the measurement of the spectral responsivity for the wavelength range 647 nm to 900 nm and, thus, **validates the prediction of the IQD and, consequently, the prediction of the spectral responsivity in this wavelength range.**

Figure 3 of **Paper 1** also shows a discrepancy at the longer wavelengths 950 nm, 975 nm and 1000 nm which lets us assume at that time that the assumption $\alpha(\lambda) \approx 0$ is not valid in that range. We therefore utilised the effect that long wavelength radiation is reflected by the front side and the rear surface of induced junction photodiodes and leads to measurable interference effects when slightly changing the wavelength to estimate the reflection loss $\alpha(\lambda)$ of long-wavelength radiation which is partly reflected by the aluminium layer on the rear surface and partly absorbed by this aluminium layer.

Paper 2 describes the corresponding investigation. Figure 4 of **Paper 2** shows that the estimation of the power absorbed in the backside aluminium layer of the induced-junction photodiodes completely explains the difference between the **predicted IQD and the measured EQD shown in Figure 3 of Paper 1** for wavelengths equal or longer than 950 nm. **Figure 5 of Paper 2 shows that, as the paper also concludes, 'the high-**

accuracy prediction of photodiode response can be extended' from 900 nm 'to at least 1031 nm with an uncertainty below 0.1%'.

Paper 3 describes the development of a model for the quantum yield in silicon photodiodes which 'is done by calculating distribution functions of charge carriers over available energy range and probabilities of charge carriers to generate secondary carriers.' The values of the modelled excess quantum yield $y(\lambda) - 1$ of Silicon are compared with the measured excess quantum yield $y_{meas}(\lambda) - 1$ calculated from the measured spectral responsivity $s_{meas}(\lambda)$ according to

$$y_{meas}(\lambda) - 1 = s_{meas}(\lambda) / \left[\left(\frac{e\lambda}{hc} \right) (1 - \rho(\lambda)) (1 - \delta_{pred}(\lambda)) \right] - 1 \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) was obtained by re-arranging eq. (3a).

The measured spectral responsivity $s_{meas}(\lambda)$ is taken from **Paper 4**, which describes PTB's measurement of the spectral responsivity of three-element reflection trap detectors against the CESR. The reflection trap detectors were set up with photodiodes fabricated within the EMPIR 18SIB10 chipS · CALe and EPM 22IEM06 S-CALe Up projects. The reflection loss of the very same three-element reflection trap detectors $\rho(\lambda)$ is taken from **Report 1**. The predicted IQD $\delta_{pred}(\lambda)$ for induced-junction photodiodes fabricated in the EMPIR 18SIB10 chipS · CALe project is taken from **Paper 1** while the predicted IQD for photodiodes fabricated in the EPM 22IEM06 S-CALe Up project is taken from **Presentation 1**.

Figure 4 of **Paper 3** shows the comparison of modeled and measured excess quantum yield in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 476 nm. It is stated in the paper: 'When comparing quantum yield of Silicon, i.e. $y_{meas}(\lambda)$, the agreement in relative terms between the modeled and measured values is better than to $\pm 2.5\%$ with the standard deviation of approximately 0.9% in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 476 nm (Fig. 5).'

The good agreement of measured and modeled or predicted quantum yield

$$y_{meas}(\lambda) \cong y_{pred}(\lambda) \quad (12)$$

also means that the predicted spectral responsivity agrees with the measured one as can be seen by substituting $y_{meas}(\lambda)$ in equation (12) by use of eq. (11)

$$s_{meas}(\lambda) / \left[\left(\frac{e\lambda}{hc} \right) (1 - \rho(\lambda)) (1 - \delta_{pred}(\lambda)) \right] \cong y_{pred}(\lambda) \quad (13)$$

re-arranging eq. (13)

$$s_{meas}(\lambda) \cong \left(\frac{e\lambda}{hc} \right) (1 - \rho(\lambda)) (1 - \delta_{pred}(\lambda)) y_{pred}(\lambda) \quad (14)$$

and realizing that the right-hand side of eq. (14) is the predicted spectral responsivity $s_{pred}(\lambda)$

$$s_{meas}(\lambda) \cong s_{pred}(\lambda) \quad (15)$$

Thus, **Paper 3** in combination with **Papers 1 and 4** and **Report 1** also validates the predicted spectral responsivity in the wavelength range 200 nm to 476 nm.

In summary, the attached papers and report describe the prediction of the spectral responsivity of PQEDs in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 476 nm and 647 nm to 1031 nm and validate the prediction by comparing it with the spectral responsivity measured against the established primary detector standard for optical radiant power, the Cryogenic Electrical Substitution Radiometer.

The deliverable is fully achieved except for uncertainties close to 200 nm and the validation at wavelengths longer than 1031 nm. The deliverable is therefore partially achieved.

2 Attachments

2.1 Paper 1: Simulation of spectral responsivity of predictable quantum efficient detector based on induced-junction photodiodes passivated with SiO₂/SiN_x

Journal Title

ARTICLE TYPE

Crossmark

Simulation of spectral responsivity of predictable quantum efficient detector based on induced-junction photodiodes passivated with SiO₂/SiN_x

RECEIVED
dd Month Year

REVISED
dd Month Year

ACCEPTED
dd Month Year

PUBLISHED
dd Month Year

Beibei Kong¹, Trinh Tran^{1,*}, Lutz Werner², Ulrike Linke², and Jarle Gran¹

¹Justervesenet, Kjeller, Norway

²Affiliation

*Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: ttr@justervesenet.no

Keywords: PQED, simulation, spectral responsivity

Abstract

In this paper, we present a method to determine the spectral responsivity of a predictable quantum efficient detector (PQED) based on SiO₂/SiN_x passivated induced-junction photodiodes, using a 3D charge carrier transport simulation model fitted to measured photocurrent-voltage data. The simulation model is built using the Cogenda Genius Device Simulator for a quarter-symmetry structure of the photodiode active area. The simulation is fitted to the photocurrent-voltage measurements of PQED at three wavelengths: 435 nm, 647 nm and 799 nm at various power levels between 100 μW and 2000 μW. We show that a single set of photodiode parameters (fixed charge density, surface recombination velocity, bulk carrier lifetime and substrate doping concentration) can reproduce the measured photocurrent curves at all three wavelengths and power levels, demonstrating the robustness of the model. Except for the lower bulk carrier lifetime, the other three fitted parameters are in perfect agreement with the values obtained by an alternative characterisation method used during the development of the photodiodes. The possible reasons for the discrepancy in bulk carrier lifetime are discussed. Using the fitted parameters, the internal quantum deficiency (IQD) of the PQED is predicted over the spectral range from 200 nm to 1100 nm and compared with measurements of the external quantum deficiency. The good agreement between the predicted IQD and the measurements demonstrates the capability of this simulation-based fitting approach for determining the responsivity of PQED over a wide spectral range from limited photocurrent measurements.

1. Introduction

In the last 15 years, there has been great progress in improving and simplifying optical power measurement standard detectors through the development of Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQED) [1-4]. PQEDs are almost loss free photodiodes where their responsivity is given by fundamental constants, residual reflectance and internal quantum deficiency (IQD). Both reflectance and IQD are highly predictable from material refractive indices, thicknesses in passivation layer and other material properties like fixed charge, bulk doping, bulk lifetime and surface recombination parameter [5-7].

The low losses of the PQED have made it possible to develop new experimental techniques like the dual-mode experiment where IQD can be found by purely experimental methods even at room temperature [8-10]. When developing the technology, having access to a known and ultra-low IQD turned out to be very favourable as a reference for the dual-mode experiment chasing for systematic error sources. Quantum yield has previously been assumed to be limited to the ultraviolet spectral range for silicon photodiodes. Predictable and ultra-low IQD of the PQED were instrumental to reveal that quantum yield is larger than one quite far into the visible

spectrum up to at least 470 nm [11]. Recently, the PQEDs have been used to improve and validate the modelling of the excess quantum yield in the UV down to 200 nm from first principles [12].

In addition to the predictability, the excellent temporal stability of the PQEDs, with an undetectable drift over 10 years, make them ideal as a transfer standard holding a spectral response scale with very few calibration points at an extended calibration interval [13]. It has been shown that the PQEDs used in this study are stable when exposed to UV radiation down to 300 nm but degrades when exposed to radiation below 280 nm. Other PQEDs, which are designed to be UV radiation resistive, are stable down to 200 nm [14].

This means that even if PQEDs are stable, they may change if they intentionally or unintentionally were exposed to UV radiation. Using the PQED as a standalone primary standard, it is therefore important to have independent methods that can quantify the PQED's IQD. The fabrication and structure of photodiodes used here are described by Koybasi et al [4]. We use the photocurrent change with reverse bias as an experimental approximation of the IQD of the photodiodes and fit a 3D simulation model of the IQD to the experimental approximation to extract the photodiode parameters in a similar way as previously done by Tran et al [7], where measurements at one wavelength only were sufficient to predict the responsivity over the full

Figure 1. Illustration of simulation structure.

spectral range from 400 nm to 900 nm.

We will show that independently of what radiation wavelength that is used in this study, the same set of parameters gives an excellent fit to measurement data from 435 nm to 799 nm and consistent with the alternative method exploited when developing the photodiodes in [4]. Furthermore, we predict the IQD over the full spectral range from 200 nm to 1100 nm based on the parameters found from the fit to the photocurrent curves.

2. Simulation model

We simulate the charge carrier transport of the photodiode with active area of $11 \text{ mm} \times 22 \text{ mm}$. The detailed structure of the photodiode is described in [1]. The 3D simulation model is built using Cogenda Genius Device Simulator [15]. An illustration of the simulation model is shown in Figure 1. To save computation time and memory, model of a quarter of the real photodiode structure is used for simulation. The simulation model has a size of $5500 \mu\text{m} \times 11000 \mu\text{m}$. p-doped and n-doped for electrical connection has a width of $100 \mu\text{m}$ each and have peak doping concentration of 10^{19} cm^{-3} . Silicon area has thickness of $500 \mu\text{m}$. Illumination area is located at the corner of the model to illustrate light radian in the middle of photodiode. Since it is the SiO_2 layer that in direct contact with the silicon in the device structure forming the induced junction, in the model the active area of photodiode is covered by a layer of SiO_2 with an effective fixed charge, while the SiN_x layer is not included in the model to reduce complexity. Oxide charge boundary condition is applied between Silicon and SiO_2 layer.

3. Photocurrent measurement

The measurement is performed with PQED consisting of 2 photodiodes in a light-trap configuration [1]. In this configuration, the two photodiodes are placed at 15° angle relative to each other. When the light comes in the PQED, 7 reflections of the light beam between two photodiodes helps to reduce optical reflection. In this study, only photocurrent from the first photodiode is measured. Therefore, only the first photodiode is considered in the simulation model. In the PQED, 91.1% of light intensity is absorbed by the first photodiode at 435 nm. 95.3% and 91.7% light intensity is absorbed by the first photodiode at 647 nm and at 799 nm, respectively, and these values are used in the simulation.

The photocurrent is measured for photodiode with bias voltage ranging from 0V to up to a maximum of 20 V, using laser illumination with different radiation power levels. Measurements were performed for the PQED at three wavelengths: 435 nm, 647 nm and 799 nm. The

Table 1. Parameters used in the simulation.

Parameters	Values
Fixed charge density Q_f	$1.3 \times 10^{12} \text{cm}^{-2}$
Surface Recombination velocity SRV	1500 cm/s
Bulk lifetime	5 ms
Doping concentration	$2 \times 10^{12} \text{cm}^{-3}$

experimentally determined IQD value, denoted as IQD_{measure} , will be calculated from the measured photocurrent according to Equation (1), as

$$IQD_{\text{measure}} = 1 - \frac{I(V)}{I_{\text{ideal}}}, \quad (1)$$

in which $I(V)$ is the measured photocurrent at bias voltage V , I_{ideal} is the photocurrent of an ideal photodiode with zero IQD [7]. I_{ideal} is approximated with I_{max} to get an estimate of the ideal photocurrent and the hence the IQD.

Beam size used in the experiments are measured individually for each power level at all wavelengths. The experimental beam shape is close to gaussian with a 4σ beamwidth of around 2.5 mm, but the simulation software cannot accommodate this shape. A uniform beam size is instead used that best approximates the gaussian beam for each of the simulation curves. We follow the same approximation as done in [7].

4. Results and discussion

The simulation model is fitted to photocurrent measurements at three wavelengths. The fixed charge density in SiO_2 layer, the surface recombination velocity, bulk lifetime and the doping concentration obtained from these fits are listed in Table 1. Figure 2 shows the comparison between the fitted simulation results and the experimental data at 435 nm, 647 nm and 799 nm. As shown in Figure 2, the IQD varies by several orders of magnitude as the reverse bias voltage increases, and simulation consistently reproduces this behaviour at all three wavelengths. In our simulation, we use the same set of photodiodes parameters for the three wavelengths, which demonstrates the robustness of the fitting approach.

Particularly, the corner point, i.e., the bias voltage at which the influence of recombination losses from the back side of the photodiode to the IQD becomes negligible, is correctly

reproduced at each wavelength. This agreement supports the validity of the fitted fixed charge density Q_f and the surface recombination velocity SRV. In induced junction photodiodes, the corner point is governed by the surface recombination processes and electric field established by fixed charge, which together determine the bias-dependent suppression of the surface recombination.

It is also worth mentioning that the fixed charge density obtained from the fitting process ($1.3 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) agrees well with the value extracted from capacitance–voltage measurements [4], indicating good consistency between these two fundamentally different methods. This value is notably higher than the previously reported value of SiO_2 -only passivated photodiodes [7]. The result further validates that a substantial amount of additional positive fixed charge is introduced by the SiN_x layer in the $\text{SiO}_2/\text{SiN}_x$ passivation stack.

Figure 2. Fitting of simulation model with experimental data at 435 nm (a), at 647 nm (b) and at 799 nm (c).

The bulk lifetime obtained from the present fit is 5 ms, which is lower than the value of 30 ms reported in [4]. In that work, the bulk lifetime was obtained from a 2D simulation fit to measured effective lifetime of a silicon wafers passivated on both sides. The measurement was performed using the QSSPC (quasi-steady-state photo-conductance) method. We do not yet have a clear explanation for this difference, but there could be several factors that contribute to it. First, the two methods probe the material under different operating conditions. QSSPC measurements are performed on a uniformly illuminated wafer without external electrical bias, and the illumination intensity is varied in a wide range. In contrast, our fit is based on a reverse-biased photodiode under localized laser illumination. These different operation conditions result in different levels of photo-generated carrier concentration in the material. Since recombination in silicon can depend on the carrier concentration [16], the extracted bulk lifetime may differ between the two

methods even for the same material. Second, as described in previous work on the fitting method [7], the bulk lifetime mainly affects the simulated IQD curve at low bias voltage well below the saturation voltage. And the influence of the bulk lifetime to important features of the IQD curve (such as the corner point) is weaker than that of SRV and Q_f . Thus, the bulk lifetime is less well determined by the fit and the extracted value of the bulk lifetime is more sensitive to simplifications in the model, such as the flat-top approximation of the incident beam. Third, the

Figure 3. Simulated IQD of PQED in wavelength range from 200 nm to 1100 nm. For comparison, measured external quantum deficiency (EQD) of PQED is plotted in the figure.

QSSPC measurement was performed on simple double-side-polished wafers with larger surface area, while the photodiode used in this work went through a complete complex manufacturing process. The differences of batch of wafers, dicing of the photodiodes and the thermal history may affect the bulk lifetime of the photodiode devices.

Furthermore, the fitted substrate doping concentration of $2 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ is in excellent agreement with the nominal wafer specification provided by the manufacturer [4].

At last, we predict the spectrally dependent IQD of the PQED over the range 200 nm to 1100 nm using the simulation model developed in this paper, as shown in Figure 3. In the visible range from approximately 400 nm to 800 nm, the predicted IQD decreases with increasing wavelength. This behaviour is consistent with the wavelength dependence of the optical absorption coefficient of silicon, which decreases at longer wavelengths. The reduced optical absorption coefficient allows the light to propagate deeper into the material, and results in carrier generation deeper within the substrate, away from the high-recombination near-surface region. At wavelengths below 400nm, the IQD keeps high as the photon absorption is concentrated at or near the front surface, where the recombination losses are high. At wavelengths above 800nm, the IQD increases again since carriers are generated deeper in the substrate, increasingly beyond the depletion region. Carriers generated in these regions must diffuse over longer distances to reach the junction, increasing the probability of bulk recombination and thereby reducing the collection efficiency.

The predicted result is further compared with the measurements of external losses of the PQED. As shown in Figure 3, the simulated IQD is in good agreement with the experimental measurements, demonstrating the accuracy of the model. However, at wavelengths close to 1000 nm an increased deviation between IQD and calibration points are observed. These deviations cannot be explained by recombination or reflectance losses from the PQED.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we develop a 3D charge carrier transport simulation model of an induced-junction photodiode passivated with a SiO₂/SiN_x stack. The model is fitted to experimental photocurrent-voltage measurements of a PQED with two photodiodes in a trap structure. From the fitting procedure, we obtain the fixed charge density, surface recombination velocity, bulk carrier lifetime and substrate doping concentration. We show that a single set of these four parameters can reproduce the measured I-V characteristics at 435 nm, 647 nm and 799 nm at multiple power levels with good agreement. Except for the bulk carrier lifetime, the fitted parameters agree well with those obtained using the alternative method employed during the photodiode development. Possible reasons for the lower fitted bulk lifetime are discussed in section 4.

Using the extracted parameters, the IQD of the PQED is predicted over the full spectral range from 200 nm to 1100 nm. The predicted IQD agrees with independent measurements of the external quantum deficiency, validating the effectiveness of this simulation method for predicting PQED responsivity. The method provides a pathway to independently predict IQD at a larger wavelength region from a limited number of photocurrent measurements, which is valuable for evaluating the long-term stability of PQED responsivity and enabling its use as a standalone primary standard.

Acknowledgements

The project 22IEM06 S-CALe Up has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

The simulations were performed on resources provided by Sigma2 – The National Infrastructure for High Performance Computing and Data Storage in Norway.

References

- [1] M. Sildoja et al.: “Predictable quantum efficient detector: I. Photodiodes and predicted responsivity”, *Metrologia* 50 (2013) 385 – 394 doi:10.1088/0026-1394/50/4/385
- [2] I. Müller et. al.: “Predictable quantum efficient detector: II. Characterization and confirmed responsivity” *Metrologia* 50 (2013) 395 – 401 doi:10.1088/0026-1394/50/4/395
- [3] T. Dönsberg et al: Predictable quantum efficient detector based on n-type silicon photodiodes” 2017 *Metrologia* 54 821 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1681-7575/aa85ed>
- [4] O. Koybasi *et al.*, “High Performance Predictable Quantum Efficient Detector Based on Induced-Junction Photodiodes Passivated with SiO₂/SiN_x,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 23, p. 7807, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21237807.
- [5] J. Gran et al.: “Simulations of a predictable quantum efficient detector with PC1D” *Metrologia* 49 (2012) S130-S134, doi:10.1088/0026-1394/49/2/S130
- [6] T. S. Stokkan et al.: Enhanced surface passivation of predictable quantum efficient detectors by silicon nitride and silicon oxynitride/silicon nitride stack”, *Journal of Applied Physics* 124, 214502 (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5054696>
- [7] T. Tran et al.: “Determination of the responsivity of a predictable quantum efficient detector over a wide spectral range based on a 3D model of charge carrier recombination losses”, *Metrologia* 59 (2022) 045012 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1681-7575/ac604b>
- [8] M. U. Nordsveen et al.: “Demonstration of a dual-mode Si detector as a self-calibrating device at room temperature”, *Vol. 25, No. 8 | 17 Apr 2017 | OPTICS EXPRESS* 8459 <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.25.008459>
- [9] J. H. Solheim et al.: “Room temperature dual-mode internal quantum deficiency measurement with propagated uncertainty to 0.03% (k=2)”, *Metrologia* 61 (2024) 065007 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1681-7575/ad7b24>
- [10] J. H. Solheim et. al.: “Second generation room-temperature dual-mode photodiodes with record-low uncertainties”, *Metrologia* 63 (2026) 025013 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1681-7575/ae577d>
- [11] L. Werner et. al.: “Quantum yield in induced-junction silicon photodiodes at wavelengths around 400 nm”, *Metrologia* 61 (2024) 035002 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1681-7575/ad310d>
- [12] T. Kùbarsepp et. al.: “Quantum yield of Silicon in the UV-VIS spectral range”, submitted to *Metrologia* June 2026
- [13] G. Porrovecchio et al.: “Long-term spectral responsivity stability of predictable quantum efficient detectors”, *Metrologia* 59 (2022) 065008 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1681-7575/ac938c>

- [14] T. Pohl et al.: “Cryogenic-Radiometer-Based UV Spectral Responsivity Calibration and Temporal Stability Assessment of Induced-Junction Photodiodes”, Submitted to Metrologia June 2026
- [15] Cogenda Genius Device Simulator: <https://www.cogenda.com/> (Accessed 18.06.2026)
- [16] Park, Jong Mun. Novel power devices for smart power applications. Diss. Technische Universität Wien, 2004.
-
-

2.2 Paper 2: Predicting photodiode backside losses using interference effects of photodiodes at wavelengths around 1000 nm

Predicting photodiode backside losses using interference effects of photodiodes at wavelengths around 1000 nm

Lars Kristian Skaar¹, Ulrike Linke², Johanne Heitmann Solheim¹, Trinh Tran¹, Stefan Källberg³, Benjamin Röben², Lutz Werner² and Jarle Gran¹

¹Justervesenet (JV), Kjeller, Norway

²Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Berlin, Germany

³Research Institute Sweden, (RISE), Borås, Sweden

E-mail: lks@justervesenet.no

Abstract

Predictable quantum efficient detectors (PQEDs) are optical power detectors that provide traceability for optical power measurements. These detectors exhibit excellent predictable responsivity within the visible spectral range. However, in the near-infrared (NIR) region, discrepancies between external and internal quantum deficiency lead to a reduced predictability. In this work, we employ a transfer matrix model of the photodetector stack to account for this discrepancy, attributing it to photon absorption in the back metallic layer. The model parameters were fitted to measured reflection data. The resulting model shows excellent agreement with independent validation measurements, achieving a predictability better than 0.1% up to a wavelength of 1031 nm.

Keywords: PQED, Infrared, absorption, transfer matrix, primary standard

1. Introduction

Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQEDs) are optical power detectors whose quantum efficiency can be accurately calculated over a wide spectral range. Ideally, no or only a minimal calibration is required for the PQED to be used as an optical power detector with state-of-the-art accuracy.

A PQED is realized with two induced-junction photodiodes (IJ-PDs) in a trap configuration [1,2] and is exploited from typically 300 nm to 1000 nm. Measurements show that IJ-PDs are indeed superior to conventional photodiodes in the visible range [3–7] and have a predictable response.

To achieve a reliable predictable response over the full spectral range 300 – 1000 nm, all aspects in the detection process must be considered. An important characteristic of IJ-PDs is the quantum yield (QY), i.e. the average number of generated electron–hole pairs per absorbed photon. While the QY is very close to 1 in the visible range, it can significantly

exceed unity in the blue and ultraviolet due to the creation of secondary electron-hole pairs by impact ionisation [8,9]. At the same time, the absorption coefficient decreases with wavelength so that near-infrared (NIR) photons penetrate much deeper into the IJ-PD chip with the possibility of even traveling from the front to the rear side of the chip and back, leading to interference effects. The strength of these interference effects depends on the absorption in the semiconductor layer together with the reflectance and absorption in the back metallic layer, all of which vary with wavelength. Thus, interference effects in the NIR may lead to measurement errors if they are not fully understood and accounted for.

In this work, we investigate such interference effects in the NIR for the IJ-PD described in [10] by measuring the reflectance. These measurements and a model fit are used to quantify the total reflectance losses and the internal losses caused by absorption in the back metallic layer. Furthermore,

it is investigated whether the absorption in the back metallic layer can explain the observed discrepancy between calibrations against the cryogenic radiometer and the predicted response at wavelengths around 1000 nm.

The samples used and their trap configurations are described in section 2. In section 3, we describe the experimental setup employed for conducting the experiments, while the model used to describe the measurement results is presented in section 4. The results of the measurements and the model are presented in section 5 before we conclude the paper in section 6.

2. Samples and principle of measurement

The IJ-PD type under investigation was manufactured in the project chipS·CALe (EURAMET EMPIR project 18SIB10) [10]. It is based on a p-type double side polished silicon substrate. The induced junction is created using a SiN_x thin film deposited by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD). The IJ-PD exhibits an active area of 22 mm × 11 mm and a nominal substrate thickness of 500 μm ± 10 μm. The back of the photodiode is coated with aluminium. A more detailed description of this type of IJ-PD can be found in [11].

The PQED trap configuration is given in figure 1 with PD1 and PD2 as the notation of the first and second photodiode respectively. Seven consecutive reflections are possible with the corresponding reflectance values R_i ($i = 1 \dots 7$).

Figure 1. Schematic of a detector comprised of two IJ-PDs in a PQED trap geometry with seven reflections for collimated radiation. The arrows depict the path of a ray of the impinging radiation. The incidence angle of the radiation with PD 1 is 45° and the angle between PD 1 and PD 2 is 15°. After 4 sequential reflections (red arrows), the radiation takes the same path backwards (blue arrows). The values of the reflectance associated with the seven sequential reflections are denoted R_i ($i = 1 \dots 7$).

From the separate measurement of the photocurrents I_1 and I_2 of PD 1 and PD 2, respectively, the photocurrent ratio can be expressed by a combination of reflectances R_i where $i = 1 \dots 7$, assuming both PD1 and PD2 being identical. The photocurrent I_2 of PD 2 is considered proportional to the total

absorbed power from the three interactions with the impinging beam (cf. figure 1), i.e.

$$I_2 = c[R_1(1 - R_2) + R_1R_2R_3(1 - R_4) + R_1R_2R_3R_4R_5(1 - R_6)], \quad (1)$$

where c is a constant. The total current of both PDs can be expressed as

$$I_1 + I_2 = c(1 - \prod_{i=1}^7 R_i). \quad (2)$$

With $R_5 = R_3$, $R_6 = R_2$, and $R_7 = R_1$, the relation between the reflections and photocurrents can be written as:

$$\frac{I_2}{I_1 + I_2} = \frac{R_1(1 - R_2 + R_2R_3 - R_2R_3R_4 + R_2R_3^2R_4 - R_2^2R_3^2R_4)}{1 - R_1^2R_2^2R_3^2R_4} = \Gamma \quad (3)$$

3. Experimental setup

The measurements were performed at the laser-based cryogenic radiometer calibration facility of the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) at an ambient temperature of 298 K. The experiment requires stable, narrowband near-infrared radiation for a set of consecutive wavelengths. For this purpose, a wavelength-tunable titanium-sapphire laser with a spectral linewidth of less than 100 kHz was used. The wavelength was measured by a wavelength meter (HighFinesse WS6-200) with a relative standard uncertainty of less than 1 ppm. The optical power at the PQED was approximately 100 μW. The power was stabilized to a relative variation within 10 ppm for the period of the measurement for one wavelength setting (approximately 2 min) using a monitor PD and a Pockels cell in a closed control loop.

Prior to the measurements, the trap detectors were optically aligned. The detectors were positioned using their output signal under near-infrared illumination so that the incident laser beam is centered on the input aperture. The angular alignment of the PQED trap detector was adjusted using a blue laser. At this laser wavelength, a residual reflection from the trap can be seen with the naked eye. The alignment is optimal if the incident and reflected beams are coaxial.

The photocurrents of the PDs in the PQED were measured by transimpedance amplifiers in conjunction with digital voltmeters.

4. Model

The transfer matrix method (TMM) is a rigorous formalism for calculating the reflectance and transmittance of multilayered materials. It is a mathematically convenient method which exploits the linear relationship between fields at either side of an interface, and at opposite sides of a film [12]. While the TMM was originally developed for coherent systems, it can easily be extended to allow for partly coherent reflections, in order to model reflections from a rough surface [13]. The model systems are shown in figure 2 with nominal parameters listed in table 1. The model was developed by fitting the parameters of the photodiode structure to the

experimental data. The model obtained a physical representation of the experimental photocurrent ratio measurements by calculating the corresponding reflectance ratio Γ using equation (3).

Since the model assumes perfectly parallel interfaces, the modelled interference fringes exhibited a larger amplitude than observed experimentally. The standard TMM evaluates a single phase-coherent path length. However, a real measurement utilizes a finite gaussian laser spot illuminating on a millimeter-scale footprint on the diode. Within this footprint, a linear thickness gradient was applied to model macroscopic thickness variations across the wafer. The macroscopic variation is thus implemented by integrating the TMM results over a thickness probability distribution:

$$R_{avg} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} R(d_0 + \Delta d) \frac{1}{\sigma_d \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta d^2}{2\sigma_d^2}\right) d(\Delta d) \quad (4)$$

Where R is the reflected light, d_0 is the nominal layer thickness, σ_d is the thickness variance and Δd is the physical thickness offset from the nominal value.

Figure 2. Schematic of the material x layer sequence of the IJ-PD with the corresponding thicknesses d_x .

The model consists of multiple layers and materials, resulting in many correlated parameters. To reduce the number of free parameters, only the incident angle θ_0 , the thickness variance σ_d , and thicknesses d_{SiNx} and d_{Si} were varied within a limited window during fitting. Other refractive indices were collected from published data, as seen in table 1. The refractive index of silicon was adjusted to the measurement temperature of 298 K using the temperature coefficients reported in [16].

To calculate the absorbed power in the backside aluminium layer of the photodiodes, the TMM model was used to calculate the power absorbed in, or transmitted through, the backside aluminium layer for each reflection in the trap as:

$$A_{back} = F_+ * P * (1 - R_b) \quad (5)$$

Where A_{back} is the power absorbed in the aluminium layer as a fraction of the incoming light, F_+ is the forward travelling

wave intensity from the front stack entering the substrate, P is the Beer-Lambert intensity from a single pass through the silicon substrate and R_b is the reflected intensity from the backside aluminium layer. The total absorbed power in the aluminium layer of the trap was then calculated as a sum of the power absorbed in the aluminium layer multiplied with the power hitting the detector for all seven reflections in the trap.

Table 1. Nominal photodiode parameters.

Material	Thickness		Refractive indices	
	Symbol	IJ-PD	Symbol	Sources
SiN _x	d_{SiNx}	65 nm	n_{SiNx}	Extrapolated from measured data [11]
SiO ₂	d_{SiO2}	5 nm	n_{SiO2}	Measured values [14]
Si-SiO ₂	$d_{Si-SiO2}$	1 nm	$n_{Si-SiO2}$	Tabulated values [14]
Si	d_{Si}	500 μ m	n_{Si}, κ_{Si}	Tabulated values [16]
Al	d_{Al}	Semi-infinite	n_{Al}, κ_{Al}	Tabulated values

5. Results and Discussion

The results of the reflectance measurements for the trap detector are shown in figure 3(a) for wavelengths from 974.9 nm to 975.9 nm, and in figure 3(b) for wavelengths from 1000.0 nm to 1001.1 nm.

The results show a periodic sinusoidal reflectance pattern, originating from interference between the reflections at the front and rear boundaries of the PDs. This interpretation is corroborated by the results of the model calculations also shown in figure 3, which agree very well with the measurement results.

The model parameters were fitted to the measurement data as discussed in section 4. The resulting parameter deviations are summarized in table 2. We achieved an excellent fit with only small changes in the angle and thickness parameters for the two datasets around 975 nm and 1000 nm.

Variations in the aluminium refractive index collected from different sources in literature caused only small changes in the modelled reflectance, that could be readily compensated by adjustments of the remaining fit parameters. In contrast, the calculated backside absorption in the aluminium layer showed a stronger dependence on the selected refractive index dataset. Therefore, multiple tabulated aluminium refractive index datasets were evaluated to quantify the sensitivity of the backside absorption to this parameter choice.

Due to the oscillatory nature of the interference fringes, the optimization landscape exhibits a strong periodicity across the parameter window. To robustly capture this parameter sensitivity, the calculated absorbed power in the aluminium layer is presented as an uncertainty envelope. The upper and lower limits of this envelope represent the parameter datasets yielding the maximum and minimum absorption within the expected parameter windows. The introduction of surface roughness at the Si/Al interface leads to increased absorption

in the aluminium layer. While polished silicon wafers exhibit extremely low surface roughness, the sputtered process used to deposit the aluminium layer may introduce additional surface roughness. To account for this effect, the upper bound of the absorption was modelled assuming a surface roughness with an RMS of 3 nm. This value is consistent with constraints imposed by other parameter ranges. Further increase in surface roughness results in a significant reduction in amplitude, causing the resulting silicon thickness d_{Si} to fall outside the parameter window.

The calculated fraction of absorbed power in the aluminium layer is shown in figure 4. The calculations are made with the unique set of parameters that minimized the root mean square error in the fit shown in figure 3. The absorbed power is in good agreement with the discrepancy between the EQD and IQD results, providing strong evidence that optical losses originate from absorption in the backside metallic layer.

When two IJ-PDs are employed in a trap configuration such as the one depicted in figure 1, the 7 consecutive reflections reduce the non-absorbed fraction of radiation to below 80 ppm up to 1040 nm, predicted by the fitted reflectance model. This difference is negligible compared to the aluminium layer absorption and is therefore omitted in the comparison between EQD and IQD.

To predict the absorbed power accurately, however, measurements of the refractive index of the aluminium layer must be performed, as this is the largest contributor to the uncertainty band. Despite only fitting the model using measurements around 975 nm and 1000 nm, the absorption losses can be predicted over an extended spectral range. Comparing the estimated absorbed power to EQD measurements performed at RISE Research Institutes of Sweden using a different but similar PQED confirms the prediction up to 1031 nm. The best fit is achieved for the aluminium refractive indices given in [18], giving a residual difference between modelled and measured losses of less than 0.06% as shown in figure 5. This demonstrates that the predictability of the PQED can be extended to at least 1031 nm with an uncertainty better than 0.1%.

6. Conclusions

We have demonstrated that by doing wavelength-dependent measurements of photocurrent signals from individual photodiodes in a PQED trap detector, absorption losses at the aluminium backside layer can be quantified using a TMM with fitted model parameters and tabulated refractive indices. Variations among the tabulated aluminium refractive indices cause a spread in the predicted absorption losses at longer wavelengths, but the measured responsivity at 1031 nm lies in the middle of this spread.

With this independent method, the high-accuracy prediction of photodiode response can be extended to at least 1031 nm with an uncertainty to below 0.1% and strengthens

the applicability of the PQED as a primary optical power standard in the near infrared.

Figure 3. Reflectance and photocurrent ratio calculated from equation (3) of the IJ-PD determined by measurements as a function of wavelength around 975 nm (a) and 1000 nm (b) (blue dots) and the modeling results (solid lines) fitted to the data for the aluminium refractive index from ref [18].

Figure 4. Absorbed power in the backside aluminium layer of the IJ-PD in a trap structure for different parameter sets (envelope) and the difference between the experimental EQD and the simulated IQD (red and blue dots).

The solid line is the aluminium refractive index dataset with the lowest RMSE when compared with the difference between the EQD and IQD.

Table 2: Deviation of fitting parameters from values stated in table 1 for the aluminium refractive index from ref [18].

Parameter	Relative to nominal	Parameter value
d_{SiN_x}	+2.3 %	67.0 nm
d_{SiO_2}	+20%	6 nm
$d_{\text{Si-SiO}_2}$	-	0.6 nm
d_{Si}	-1.6 %	492 μm
θ_0	-0.2%	44.9°
σ_d	-	16 nm

Figure 5: Residuals of simulated backside absorption and the difference between the EQD and IQD for the aluminium refractive index from ref [18].

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Ozhan Koybasi and Eivind Bardalen for providing the high-quality induced-junction silicon photodiodes. The research leading to these results has received funding from the EMPIR project 18SIB10 chipS CALe and from the Metrology-Partnership project 22IEM06 S-CALe Up co-financed by the Participating States and by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

References

- [1] Sildoja M, Manoocheri F, Merimaa M, Ikonen E, Müller I, Werner L, Gran J, Kübarsepp T, Smid M and Rastello M L 2013 Predictable quantum efficient detector: I. Photodiodes and predicted responsivity *Metrologia* **50** 385–94
- [2] Tran T, Porrovecchio G, Smid M, Ikonen E, Dönsberg T and Gran J 2022 Determination of the responsivity of a predictable quantum efficient detector over a wide spectral range based on a 3D model of charge carrier recombination losses *Metrologia* **59** 045012
- [3] Müller I, Johannsen U, Linke U, Socaciu-Siebert L, Smid M, Porrovecchio G, Sildoja M, Manoocheri F, Ikonen E, Gran J, Kübarsepp T, Brida G and Werner L 2013 Predictable quantum efficient detector: II. Characterization and confirmed responsivity *Metrologia* **50** 395–401
- [4] Juntunen M A, Heinonen J, Vähänissi V, Repo P, Valluru D and Savin H 2016 Near-unity quantum efficiency of broadband black silicon photodiodes with an induced junction *Nature Photon* **10** 777–81
- [5] Salfner K, Dönsberg T, Porrovecchio G, Smid M, Nield K and Nevas S 2018 Characterization of a room temperature predictable quantum efficient detector for applications in radiometry and photometry *Metrologia* **55** 654–61
- [6] Ulset M S, Bardalen E, Pepe C, Filippo R, Rajteri M, Sildoja M-M, Kübarsepp T, Gieseler J and Gran J 2022 Dual-mode room temperature self-calibrating photodiodes approaching cryogenic radiometer uncertainty *Metrologia* **59** 035008
- [7] Solheim J H, Bardalen E and Gran J 2024 Room temperature dual-mode internal quantum deficiency measurement with propagated uncertainty to 0.03% ($k = 2$) *Metrologia* **61** 065007
- [8] Korpuseenko M, Vaskuri A, Manoocheri F and Ikonen E 2023 Internal quantum efficiency of silicon photodetectors at ultraviolet wavelengths *Metrologia* **60** 055010
- [9] Werner L, Linke U, Müller I, Kübarsepp T, Sildoja M-M, Tran T and Gran J 2024 Quantum yield in induced-junction silicon photodiodes at wavelengths around 400 nm *Metrologia* **61** 035002
- [10] chipS.CALe EURAMET European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) project 18SIB10 (available at <http://chipscale.aalto.fi>) (Accessed 15 June 2026)
- [11] Koybasi O, Nordseth Ø, Tran T, Povoli M, Rajteri M, Pepe C, Bardalen E, Manoocheri F, Summanwar A, Korpuseenko M, Getz M N, Ohlckers P, Ikonen E and Gran J 2021 High Performance Predictable Quantum Efficient Detector Based on Induced-Junction Photodiodes Passivated with SiO₂/SiN_x *Sensors* **21** 7807
- [12] Skaar J and Haakestad M W 2012 Inverse scattering of dispersive stratified structures *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B, JOSAB* **29** 2438–45
- [13] Katsidis C C and Siapkias D I 2002 General transfer-matrix method for optical multilayer systems with coherent, partially coherent, and incoherent interference *Appl. Opt., AO* **41** 3978–87
- [14] White M, Lolli L, Brida G, Gran J and Rajteri M 2013 Optical constants and spatial uniformity of thermally grown oxide layer of custom, induced-junction, silicon photodiodes for a predictable quantum efficient detector *Journal of Applied Physics* **113** 243509
- [15] Schinck C, Christian Peest P, Schmidt J, Brendel R, Bothe K, Vogt M R, Kröger I, Winter S, Schirmacher A, Lim S, Nguyen H T and MacDonald D 2015 Uncertainty analysis for the coefficient of band-to-band absorption of crystalline silicon *AIP Advances* **5** 067168
- [16] Green M A 2008 Self-consistent optical parameters of intrinsic silicon at 300 K including temperature coefficients *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* **92** 1305–10
- [17] McPeak K M, Jayanti S V, Kress S J P, Meyer S, Iotti S, Rossinelli A and Norris D J 2015 Plasmonic Films Can Easily Be Better: Rules and Recipes *ACS Photonics* **2** 326–33

-
- [18] Rakić A D 1995 Algorithm for the determination of intrinsic optical constants of metal films: application to aluminum *Appl. Opt.*, **AO 34** 4755–67
- [19] Ordal M A, Bell R J, Alexander R W, Newquist L A and Querry M R 1988 Optical properties of Al, Fe, Ti, Ta, W, and Mo at submillimeter wavelengths *Appl. Opt.*, **AO 27** 1203–9
- [20] Mathewson A G and Myers H P 1971 Absolute Values of the Optical Constants of Some Pure Metals *Phys. Scr.* **4** 291
- [21] Cheng F, Su P-H, Choi J, Gwo S, Li X and Shih C-K 2016 Epitaxial Growth of Atomically Smooth Aluminum on Silicon and Its Intrinsic Optical Properties *ACS Nano* **10** 9852–60

2.3 Paper 3: Quantum yield of Silicon in the UV-VIS spectral range

Journal Title

OPEN ACCESS

Crossmark

Quantum yield of Silicon in the UV-VIS spectral range

RECEIVED
dd Month Year**Toomas Kübarsepp^{1*}, Meelis-Mait Sildoja¹, Jaanus Vahi¹, Aarre Kilpeläinen², Farshid Manoocheri², Peter Meindl³, Tobias Pohl³, Lutz Werner³, Marek Šmid⁴, Geiland Porrovecchio⁴, Trinh Tran⁵, Jarle Gran⁵, and Erkki Ikonen^{2,6}**REVISED
dd Month Year¹AS Metrosert, Tallinn, Estonia²Aalto University, Metrology Research Institute, Espoo, Finland³Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Berlin, Germany⁴Czech Metrology Institute, Prague, Czech Republic⁵Justervesenet, Kjeller, Norway⁶VTI MIKES, Espoo, FinlandACCEPTED
dd Month YearPUBLISHED
dd Month Year

*Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: toomas.kubarsepp@metrosert.ee**Keywords:** optical metrology, Silicon, quantum yield, ultraviolet

Abstract

The essential steps for simulating quantum yield of Silicon have been thoroughly studied in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 480 nm. We have estimated separately excess quantum yield contributions arising from primary carriers created after photon absorption by using Quantum Espresso software. This is done by calculating distribution functions of charge carriers over available energy range and probabilities of charge carriers to generate secondary carriers. The resulting quantum yield values are compared to those of obtained by using the high-accuracy measurement data of different types of Silicon-based Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQED) indicating better than to $\pm 2.5\%$ relative agreement within spectral interval from 200 nm to 476 nm.

1. Introduction

The advances in optical technologies need continuous improvement of metrological methods and standards for a wide range of application areas. In optical measurements, semiconductor photodetectors are strong candidates for absolute standard detectors owing to low uncertainty, compact size and reasonable cost. In the visible and near infrared wavelength range, the new type of absolute photodetectors – Predictable Quantum Efficient Photodetector (PQED) based on special Silicon photodiodes has been demonstrated to be stable possessing predictable responsivity with extremely low uncertainty [1, 2, 3]. Extending PQED applications awaken need for physically justified model of quantum yield of Silicon which exceeds unity in the ultraviolet spectral range.

Over decades, several research groups have made efforts to derive from first principles the number of excess charge carriers after absorption of a photon [4, 5, 6, 7]. The attempts to elaborate a model for quantum yield in Silicon over wide spectral range were hampered by simplifications, e.g. parabolic band structure, equal distribution of excess kinetic energy between electrons and holes, and/or lack of accurate measurement data to compare with. In recent years, the research work on the elaboration of physically sound model for quantum yield of Silicon has been re-activated [8, 9] owing to improved measurement methods and facilities providing new and accurate responsivity measurement results [10]. The focus has been on calculation and prediction of the quantum yield in Silicon exceeding unity after absorption of a photon with sufficient energy. Yet again, simplified interpolation functions have been elaborated targeting ease-of-use of the quantum yield in spectral responsivity calculations in the UV-wavelength range.

Many earlier simplifying assumptions can be overcome using modern tools for band structure analysis and optical properties calculation. In the current work, we describe methods for Silicon excess quantum yield modeling from first principles and present calculation results by using open-source software Quantum Espresso (QE) [11]. We compare our model to the values derived from high-accuracy measured spectral responsivity recently became available. Also, we discuss our proposed model for excess quantum yield and further opportunities for improvement.

2. Method

To evaluate excess quantum yield in Silicon, $y(h\nu)-1$, we have used an approach describing contributions arising separately from carriers created after photon absorption event [4]:

$$y(h\nu) - 1 = \int dE [N_c(E)P_c(h\nu, E) + N_v(E)P_v(h\nu, E)] \quad (1)$$

where $h\nu$ is photon energy, $N_c(E)$ and $N_v(E)$ are the average numbers of carrier pairs created by impact ionization caused by a primary electron and hole, respectively. The symbols $P_c(h\nu, E)$ and $P_v(h\nu, E)$ denote distributions of electrons and holes, respectively, over excess kinetic energy E after the absorption of photon. The integration is performed over available kinetic energy E .

To evaluate both, average numbers of carrier pairs and distribution functions of primary carriers generated due to photon absorption, the band structure of Silicon has to be known. There are several methods from first principles to calculate band structure [12]. We have used pseudopotential method offered by open-source Quantum Espresso (QE) framework with self-consistent calculations within Density-Functional Theory (DFT) and applying a Projector-Augmented Wave-type (PAW) pseudopotential [11], which has been investigated by other research groups, e.g. [13, 14], and is being constantly improved in terms of physical aspects, as well as computational accuracy and speed [15]. However, due to well-known DFT band gap problem [16], QE recalculates the Fermi energy when performing the non self-consistent calculation and this could lead to band gap variations from 0.5 eV to 0.64 eV for Silicon rather than experimentally derived value of 1.123 eV. Although in optical transitions only energy difference in between valence and conduction bands matters, care should be taken to follow the Fermi energy used and reported during QE calculations to properly locate top of the uppermost valence band for correct carrier energy counting. In our calculations, we have used Fermi energy $E_F=6.505$ eV provided by QE and corrected the obtained calculated indirect band gap value 0.640 eV rigidly by 0.483 eV. In the present paper, we count energy of holes from the uppermost valence band and energy of electrons from the lowest conductance band, unless mentioned otherwise.

2.1. Energy distribution functions of primary carriers $P_i(E)$

The distribution functions of electrons $P_c(h\nu, E)$ and holes electrons $P_v(h\nu, E)$ over kinetic energy E are obtained by using linear-analytic-tetrahedron-method (LATM) [17]. The idea of the LATM is to subdivide the volume of integration into tetrahedral micro cells where wavevector k and energy E are determined exactly at the corners. It is then assumed that k and E vary linearly between the corners, after which the integral over each micro cell may be carried out analytically [18]. To do this, the volume integral is rewritten as a surface integral over surfaces of constant energy in the Brillouin Zone, making the integral independent of the shape of the cell. The contribution from each tetrahedron is then calculated and added

together, to get the result for the entire Irreducible Brillouin Zone (IBZ). The IBZ sub-mesh that we used consists of 256 tetrahedra.

This method effectively turns line integral in two-dimensional Brillouin Zone into a sum of analytic expressions that require only energy values at k -points at the vertices of tetrahedra. The calculation method by LATM includes transition matrix elements at the vertices of

tetrahedra. In the calculations, we have used equal transition matrix elements based on constant-matrix-element approximation [19].

The calculations of the distribution functions $P_i(h\nu, E)$ have been performed over interval of kinetic energy $0 < E < h\nu - E_g$, available for a generated carrier after absorption of a photon with energy $h\nu$. The index $i=c, v$ denotes electron or hole, respectively. The symbol $E_g=1.123$ eV stands for band gap of Silicon.

Quantum Espresso provides energy values at user specified k -points for calculation of the distribution functions $P_i(h\nu, E)$. We calculated the normalized distribution functions for electrons $P_c(h\nu, E)$ and holes $P_v(h\nu, E)$ separately and examples of distribution functions at some photon wavelengths are illustrated in Fig. 1. In general, it can be observed that kinetic energy is more likely distributed to created electrons at low photon energy. As photon energy increases, the excess kinetic energy is re-distributed between created electrons and holes.

2.2. Average numbers of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$

The average numbers of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$ can be calculated as [20]:

$$N_i(E) = \left[1 + \frac{r'_i(E)}{r_i(E)} \right]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where the index $i=c, v$ denotes electron or hole, respectively, $r'_i(E)$ is electron (or hole)-phonon scattering rate. The symbol $r_i(E)$ stands for electron (or hole) impact ionization rate. The average number of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$ according to Eq(2) is valid only if primary particle with energy E will decay to zero energy without ionization scattering or will be origin of one impact ionization event.

In several studies on quantum yield modeling [6, 7, 8, 9] both, the carrier-phonon scattering rate and impact ionization rate estimation trace back to pioneering work described in [20]. However, Alig et al derived the rates based on parabolic and isotropic band structure, which is not always the case for Silicon [21]. Furthermore, scattering rates and impact ionization rates were treated equal for electrons and holes.

Later research has shown that both, the impact ionization rates [22, 23] and the phonon scattering rates are different for electrons and holes [13, 14].

For electrons, we adopted simulation method for the impact ionization rate described in [22] and recently confirmed by experiments [24]. According to this method, the impact ionization rate for electrons in units 1/s can be calculated as:

$$r_c(E) = 1 \cdot 10^{11} \cdot (E - \varepsilon_c)^{4.6} \quad (3)$$

where E is electron energy in units eV and $\varepsilon_c=1.1$ eV. The above Eq(3) for practical use was obtained by least-square-fitting to the numerical Monte Carlo simulation results of impact

ionization rate of electrons in Silicon derived from wave functions and band structure based on an empirical pseudopotential method.

In the calculations of the impact ionization rate in units 1/s for holes, we use the method showing similar shape as for electrons, yet with different values of parameters:

$$r_v(E) = 2 \cdot 10^{12} \cdot (E - \varepsilon_v)^{4.0} \quad (4)$$

where E is hole energy in units eV and $\varepsilon_v=1.6$ eV. The parameter values in Eq(4) for practical use were obtained by least-square-fitting to the numerical Monte Carlo simulation results of impact ionization rate of holes in Silicon [23].

We use previously published carrier-phonon scattering rates obtained with the help of QE [13]. The theoretical framework and calculation details are given in [13], nevertheless, we corrected the band gap of Silicon to $E_g=1.123$ eV as depicted in Fig. 2.

By combining the carrier-phonon scattering rates $r'_i(E)$ and impact ionization rates $r_i(E)$, we obtained average numbers of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$ (Fig 3) using Eq(2). For illustration purposes, the rates of electron-phonon scattering and hole-phonon scattering are embedded. As can be seen, the baselines of average numbers $N_i(E)$ are closely guided by the carrier impact ionization

rates $r_i(E)$. This is expected, because carrier-phonon scattering rates $r_i'(E)$ are less energy dependent (Fig. 2) as compared to that of impact ionization rates of both, electrons and holes.

Also, we notice that the average number of electrons $N_c(E)$ and holes $N_v(E)$ are different.

3. Results

Using Eq(1) to integrate the estimated average numbers of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$ and the distribution functions of carriers $P_i(h\nu, E)$ over appropriate limits determined by excess energy E , the expected excess of quantum yield $y(h\nu)-1$ of Silicon is obtained (Fig. 4). Over the wavelength range from 200 nm to 480 nm the calculation step of excess quantum yield is 5 nm. The actual cut-off of the modeled excess quantum yield is at about 479.3 nm-wavelength owing to the Fermi energy $E_F=6.505$ eV we used in the calculations of carrier distribution functions $P_i(h\nu, E)$.

We compare the modeled excess quantum yield to the accurate values obtained using special type of photodetectors – Predictable Quantum Efficient Photodetectors (PQED) composed of stable Silicon-based photodiodes. The PQED photodiodes are induced-junction photodiodes made of high purity silicon wafer doped by about $2 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and passivated by either thermally grown SiO_2 without [1, 2] or with plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposited (PECVD) SiN_x thin film on top of thermally grown SiO_2 -layer [24]. The relationship between the responsivity of semiconductor photodetector, losses (internal quantum deficiency and reflectance) and quantum yield can be found elsewhere, e.g. [8, 9]. In such a way, the quantum yield values have been derived in [8, 9, 25, 26] and we used the same method estimating the

losses [27] to obtain values of quantum yield from high-accuracy measured responsivity data described in [28]. The comparison results are presented in Figs 4 and 5.

The good agreement between the modeled and measured values of excess quantum yield $y(h\nu)-1$ can be noticed over the studied range of photon energy. Some increase in discrepancy between the modelled and measured values can be observed at low photon energies below 3.0 eV. On the other hand, the uncertainty in the modeled values is high at low photon energies, which is discussed in Section 4.

When comparing quantum yield of Silicon, i.e. $y(h\nu)$, the agreement in relative terms between the modeled and measured values is better than to $\pm 2.5\%$ with the standard deviation of approximately 0.9% in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 476 nm (Fig. 5).

4. Discussion

The calculation of excess quantum yield according to Eq (1) involves number of parameters which are determined based on theoretical frameworks, semi-empirical considerations and measurement results. The parameters are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. List of parameters used in excess quantum yield calculations using Equation 1.

Parameter	Equation	Value	Reference	Variation
Fermi energy (eV)	(1), (2)	6.505	[11]	± 0.150 eV
Multiplication factor (1/s)	(3)	$1 \cdot 10^{11}$	[22]	$\pm 10\%$
Threshold ε (eV)	(3)	1.1	[22]	$\pm 10\%$
Exponent	(3)	4.6	[22, 25]	$\pm 2\%$
Multiplication factor (1/s)	(4)	$2 \cdot 10^{12}$	[23]	$\pm 10\%$
Threshold ε_v (eV)	(4)	2.0	[23]	$\pm 10\%$
Exponent	(4)	4.0	[23]	$\pm 2\%$

The Fermi energy is recalculated when Quantum Espresso performs the non self-consistent calculation and this could lead to variations by about ± 0.15 eV. We have conducted calculations of excess quantum yield and estimated that the relative change can be about 6% at photon energy 6.2 eV and about 40% at photon energy 2.6 eV in the excess quantum yield. At low photon energy values, the relative change seems to be huge; on the other hand, the modeled excess quantum yield is small, e.g. $y(h\nu)-1=130$ ppm at photon energy of 2.6 eV.

In addition, knowing Fermi energy is important when studying real photodiode structures as Fermi energy can change due to semiconductor doping [21]. This may increase concentration of electrons in conductance band minimum ready to receive excess kinetic energy. The Fermi energy can depend on electric field in a photodiode, as well, introducing further challenges in calculations of excess quantum yield. The knowledge about exact estimates of quantum yield in real photodiode structures is still to be improved.

In the calculations of carrier distribution function $P_i(h\nu, E)$ we have used resolution of 0.01 eV to optimize the calculation speed. The corresponding wavelength resolution can be up to 2 nm at longer light wavelengths. Introducing higher resolution may increase calculation accuracy, especially at around photon wavelengths at which quantum yield becomes to exceed unity.

The calculation of carrier impact ionization rates $r_i(E)$ includes parameters whose values are obtained by least-square-fitting to the first-principle numerical simulations [22, 23]. The estimated variation intervals of those parameter values are listed in Table 1. The corresponding relative variation in excess quantum yield is 10%, almost uniform in the wavelength range studied.

Last but not least, the carrier-phonon scattering rates are adopted from previously published data [13]. The resolution of 0.001 eV has been used in those calculations, while we extract data with resolution of 0.01 eV needed to match the resolution of carrier distribution

function $P_i(h\nu, E)$. Although, integration over energy interval diminishes the influence arising from difference between calculation and extraction resolution of the carrier-phonon scattering rates, the contribution to the relative variation in excess quantum yield could span from 3% at 200-nm photon wavelength to about 30% at 479-nm photon wavelength.

By combining the variation of the parameters listed in Table 1, the variation of excess quantum yield is estimated and illustrated by dashed lines in Fig. 4. In relative terms, the variation in excess quantum yield is about 20% almost uniform up to the wavelength of 410 nm and increases to 50% at the wavelength of 479 nm. In absolute terms, the variation is 0.100 at 200-nm photon wavelength and gradually decreases to 0.00030 at 479-nm photon wavelength. At those wavelengths, the modeled excess quantum yield is 0.570 and 0.00013, respectively.

The modeled and measured excess quantum yield exhibits slightly complicated structure above photon energy of 4 eV peaking at about 4.32 eV (Fig. 4). This phenomenon has been previously related to pronounced contribution by holes [6].

At photon energy 4.32 eV we calculated carrier distribution functions $P_i(h\nu, E)$ (Fig. 6) and found that there is a clear peak in the distribution of electrons at maximum kinetic energy. In conjunction with average number of carrier pairs created by electrons $N_c(E)$, the electron distribution function $P_c(h\nu, E)$ makes higher contribution to the excess quantum yield as compared to that of holes. This can be supported by referring to Silicon band structure where many carrier pairs are generated in direct transitions around Γ_2' -point giving the major fraction of the excess kinetic energy to the electrons.

The modeled excess quantum yield of Silicon shows a small dip around the photon energy of 4.62 eV ($\lambda=268$ nm) (Fig. 4). As we notice, there is analogous decrease in average number of carrier pairs created by electrons $N_c(E)$ close to this photon energy. In the same situation, no significant re-distribution of energy is observed between the functions $P_c(h\nu, E)$ and $P_v(h\nu, E)$ (Fig. 6). By referring to Silicon band structure, it can be explained by absorption of a photon with energy around 4.62 eV resulting mostly in indirect transitions, which causes increased probability for carrier-phonon scattering.

5. Conclusions

The quantum yield of Silicon has been studied and model derived from first principles in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 480 nm. We found it useful to calculate separately contributions arising from primary electrons and holes generated after photon absorption. The probabilities of charge carriers over available kinetic energy range and probabilities of charge carriers to generate secondary carriers were estimated. We applied pseudopotential method available from open-source Quantum Espresso software platform.

Our calculations show that the distribution functions of electrons $P_c(h\nu, E)$ and holes $P_v(h\nu, E)$ over available kinetic energy $E=h\nu-E_g$ are not necessarily equal. For example, at low photon energy most of the excess kinetic energy is received by electrons. This can be useful to simplify calculation of excess quantum yield $y(h\nu)-1$ in the photon energy range from about 2.5 eV to 3.2 eV, i.e. including direct transitions at Γ -point, by relying on impact ionization initiated by electrons only as experimentally verified in [25]. On the other hand, at higher photon energy the separate handling of distribution functions of carriers assists to understand physical processes in Silicon.

The estimates of average number of carrier pairs $N_i(E)$ include the carrier-phonon scattering rates $r'_i(E)$ and impact ionization rates initiated $r_i(E)$ by primary carrier generated. We can support that in the calculations of the rates the realistic Silicon band structure has to be used.

Our modeled excess quantum yield of Silicon is compared to the values derived from high-accuracy measured spectral responsivity data [8, 9, 25, 26, 28]. The comparison shows that, in

absolute terms, the agreement is better than to ± 0.02 at the wavelength of 200 nm and about ± 0.0002 at the wavelength of 476 nm.

Nevertheless, there are several possibilities to improve accuracy of modeling, e.g. by increasing sub-mesh of Silicon irreducible Brillouin Zone, by using higher energy resolution in the calculations, and, when it comes to real photodiode structures, the effects of doping profile and induced electric field on quantum yield are useful to consider.

Acknowledgements

The project 22IEM06 S-CALe Up has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

meta data for submission: Funder name: European Partnership on Metrology; Funder ID: 10.13039/100019599; Grant number: 22IEM06 S-Cale Up)

References

- [1] Sildoja M. et al. (2013) *Metrologia* **50** 385 – 394.
- [2] Müller I. et al. (2013) *Metrologia* **50** 395 – 401.
- [3] Tran T et al (2022) *Metrologia* **59** 045012.
- [4] Geist J and Wang, C.S. (1983) *Phys. Rev. B* **27** 4841–4847.
- [5] Durant N.M. and Fox N.P. (1993) *Metrologia* **30** 345-350.
- [6] Wolf M et al (1998) *J. App. Phys.* **83** 4213.
- [7] Ramanathan K and Kurinsky N (2020) *Physical Review D* **102** 063026.
- [8] Korpusenko M. et al. (2023) *Metrologia* **60** 055010.
- [9] Werner L. et al. (2024) *Metrologia* **61** 035002.
- [10] Meindl P (2006) et al *Metrologia* **43** 72–77.
- [11] Giannozzi P et al (2017) *J.Phys.: Condens.Matter* **29** 465901.
- [12] Yu P.Y and Cardona M (2005) *Fundamentals of Semiconductors 3rd Ed* 58-105
- [13] Tandon N et al (2015) *J. App. Phys.* **118** 045713.
- [14] Poncé S et al (2016) *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **209** 116.
- [15] Carnimeo I et al (2023) *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **19** 6992–7006.
- [16] Mori-Sanchez et al (2008) *PRL* **100** 146401
- [17] Wang C S and Freeman A J (1979) *Phys.Rev.B* **19** 793–805.
- [18] Westerkam A M et al (2021) *The 8th Student symposium on mechanical and manufacturing engineering*, Aalborg, Denmark.
- [19] Sano N and Yoshii A (1995) *J. Appl. Phys.* **77** 2020.
- [20] Alig R C et al (1980) *Phys. Rev. B* **22** 5565–5581.
- [21] Sze S M and Kwok K NG (2007) *Physics of Semiconductor Devices 3rd Ed* 12-27.
- [22] Kamakura Y et al. (1994) *J.Appl.Phys.* **75** 3500.
- [23] Fischetti M V et al (1996) *International Conference on Simulation of Semiconductor Processes and Devices SISPAD '96 (IEEE Cat. No.96TH8095)* 43-44.
- [24] Koybasi O et al (2021) *Sensors* **21(23)** 7807.
- [25] Kilpeläinen A et al (2026) *J. Appl. Phys.*, submitted.
- [26] Porrovecchio G et al (2026) *CMI ScaleUP PQED 44-54 vs CR in UV, Report to S-Cale Up project.*
- [27] Tran T et al (2026) *W44 – SCALe Up photodiode Report to S-Cale Up project.*
- [28] Pohl T et al (2026) *Metrologia submitted*

2.4 Paper 4: Cryogenic-Radiometer-Based UV Spectral Responsivity Calibration and Temporal Stability Assessment of Induced-Junction Photodiodes

Cryogenic-Radiometer-Based UV Spectral Responsivity Calibration and Temporal Stability Assessment of Induced-Junction Photodiodes

Tobias Pohl¹, Peter Meindl¹, Ozhan Koybasi², Michael N. Getz², Eivind Bardalen³,
Meelis-Mait Sildoja⁴, Jarle Gran⁵, and Lutz Werner¹

¹Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Berlin, Germany

²SINTEF, Oslo, Norway

³University of South-Eastern Norway (USN), Borre, Norway

⁴Metrosert, Tallinn, Estonia

⁵Justervesenet (JV), Kjeller, Norway

June 8, 2026

Abstract

The Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) has updated one of its cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer facilities with a laser-driven light source for SI-traceable detector calibrations of the spectral responsivity in the UV wavelength range from 200 nm to 410 nm. Several detectors equipped with silicon photodiodes have been calibrated with relative standard measurement uncertainties of about 0.1% at this facility. These measurements have been performed in order to investigate the temporal stability of the photodiodes' spectral responsivity over a time frame of 2 months to about 2 years. Some photodiodes show significant degradation, whereas others are stable within the measurement uncertainty. The calibration of the spectral responsivity of these photodiodes furthermore provides the basis for evaluating their suitability for utilization as primary detector standards, so called Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQEDs).

1 Introduction

In the last decades, cryogenic electrical substitution radiometers (CESRs) have been the gold standard in primary reference measurement procedures for the measurement of radiant power in the ultraviolet (UV), visible (VIS) and infrared (IR) part of the spectrum [1] and thus for the calibration of radiation detectors in view of their spectral responsivity. The spectral responsivity $s(\lambda)$ describes the detector's electrical response - which is the photocurrent I_{ph} in case of a photodiode - on incident optical radiant power Φ of the wavelength λ :

$$s(\lambda) = \frac{I_{\text{ph}}}{\Phi} \quad (1)$$

However, operating a CESR is labour-intensive and requires considerable time, infrastructure and expertise. Therefore, the development of so-called self-calibrating photodiodes – also known as Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQEDs) – serving as primary detector standards could take absolute radiometry to the next level in terms of simplicity and availability of SI-traceable radiant power measurement: Accurate measurement and/or simulation

of photodiode key parameters enables to calculate the spectral responsivity $s_{\text{calc}}(\lambda)$ depending on the vacuum wavelength λ using the following fundamental equation:

$$s_{\text{calc}}(\lambda) = \frac{e \cdot \lambda}{h \cdot c} \cdot (1 - \rho(\lambda)) \cdot (1 - \delta(\lambda)) \cdot y(\lambda) \quad (2)$$

Eq. 2 is based on the fundamental constants elementary charge e , vacuum speed of light c and Planck’s constant h , along with the photodiode key parameters quantum yield y , reflectivity ρ and internal recombination losses δ [2].

Within the EMPIR 18SIB10 chipS-CALe [3] and EPM 22IEM06 S-CALe Up [4] projects, silicon photodiodes were fabricated and their aforementioned key parameters were determined for the first time in the UV and short VIS range [5, 6, 7, 8], enabling calculation of $s_{\text{calc}}(\lambda)$ according to Eq. 2. The above-mentioned projects focus on so-called induced-junction photodiodes, which exhibit reduced internal recombination losses that are easier to compute [9]. The majority of the studied photodiodes are therefore induced-junction photodiodes, as shown in Tab. 1 and 2. In addition, some externally doped photodiodes are included to provide comparability.

However, this approach of self-calibrating photodiode standards is only as accurate and feasible as

- their photodiode key parameters are once verified by accurate measurements against CESRs and
- the temporal stability of the photodiodes’ spectral responsivity is verified, as aging is a known problem of UV photodiodes [10, 11].

For these reasons, three-element reflection trap detectors have been set up with the aforementioned photodiodes, and their spectral responsivity $s_{\text{meas}}(\lambda)$ has been measured against PTB’s CESR over a period of up to 22 months.

2 Set up of three-element reflection trap detectors and calibration scheme

The use of photodiodes in a three-element reflection trap design combines reduced reflection losses - achieved through multiple specular reflections (five in the present design) - with a spatially uniform detector response that is insensitive to the polarisation of the incident radiation [12].

PTB’s detector design is depicted in Fig. 1, which is equipped with an aperture with a nominal diameter of 8 mm, that can be replaced by an aperture as required by different measurement facilities. It provides individual readout of each of the three photodiodes or, via an adapter cable, parallel readout of all photodiodes. The detector’s temperature can be varied using liquid-based heat transfer through a metal hose, and monitored with the integrated Pt100 temperature sensor.

Tab. 1 lists the amount and type of studied photodiodes alongside the realised time frame and calibration wavelength range. The spectral step-width was typically 5 nm. Tab. 1 also specifies the wafer origin. Note that the wafers listed from the chipS-CALe project are nominally identical, whereas within the S-CALe Up project different wafers are fabricated differently. More detailed information on the photodiode fabrication process and layer structures can be found in Tab. 2 and [13, 14]. The photodiodes have a nominal sensitive area of 11 mm x 11 mm. They all have been packaged to match PTB’s detector design.

The TC1, TC2, TC3 and TC4 detectors, which are equipped with chipS-CALe photodiodes, were ready for measurement as early as June 2024. This enabled a temporal stability

Figure 1: Three-element reflection trap detector in partially section view (a). Orientation of the three photodiodes (depicted in orange), resulting in five reflections within the detector. Incident radiation is visualised in light red (b). Set-up of the detector (c).

Table 1: Overview of investigated photodiodes including the measurement time frame and calibration wavelength range. The detector name is PTB-given and will be used for identification purposes within this publication. Photodiodes named TC originate from the chipS-CALe project, while the S in the name indicates origin from the S-CALe Up project. Photodiodes from wafers marked with * are not induced-junction photodiodes, but externally doped, see Tab. 2 for more information. Measurements were usually conducted starting at the shorter wavelength and proceeding in 5 nm steps to the upper wavelength limit. However, the TC2 measurements marked with ** were each performed in two consecutive spectral intervals: The range from 300 nm to 410 nm was measured first, followed by the range from 200 nm to 300 nm.

Name	Wafer#	Calibration wavelength range / nm						
		2024 June	2025 June	2025 November	2026 February	2026 March	2026 April	2026 May
TC1	15/15/17	300 - 410	300 - 410					
TC2	15/15/17	300 - 410	300 - 410		200 - 410**	200 - 410**		
TC3	20/17/20	280 - 410	280 - 410			280 - 410		280 - 410
TC4	20/20/15	280 - 410	280 - 410			280 - 410		280 - 410
TS1	10*			200 - 410				
TS2	13*			200 - 410		200 - 410		
TS3	41			200 - 410			200 - 410	
TS4	6*				200 - 410			
TS5	43				200 - 410			
TS6	44				200 - 410		200 - 410	

study to be conducted over a time period of almost two years, involving four consecutive measurements. However, pre-testing of these photodiodes revealed degradation due to UV irradiation below 280 nm. Therefore, these photodiodes were only measured at wavelengths equal or longer than 280 nm (TC1), and as a precaution, from 300 nm and above (TC3, TC4). TC2 was also only measured at wavelengths equal or longer than 280 nm in the first three rounds. However, in the 3rd and 4th round additional measurements down to 200 nm were performed with this detector despite the risk of UV-induced degradation. The results will be presented and discussed in Sect. 4.3.

Due to the time-consuming production process of the S-CALe Up photodiodes, the temporal stability of these photodiodes could only be studied over a time period of two months (TS6) to five months (TS3) to date.

TC1 was not measured a third time, and TS1, TS4 and TS5 were not measured a second time, in order to reduce calibration time and focus on the most promising detectors.

Table 2: Overview of investigated photodiodes and some of their fabrication details. For the passivation of some photodiodes, Plasma-Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition (PECVD) is applied. Photodiodes without an implant species are induced-junction photodiodes. For more information, see [14], however, some of the production details are confidential.

Name	Wafer#	Project	Passivation process	Implant species	Crystal orientation
TC1	15/15/17	chipS-CALe	6 nm thermal SiO ₂ ; deposit 65 nm PECVD SiN _x	None	Si(100)
TC2	15/15/17				
TC3	20/17/20				
TC4	20/20/15				
TS1	10	S-CALe Up	anneal at 900 °C for 10 min; leave 15 nm screening oxide; deposit 22 nm PECVD SiN _x	As	Si(100)
TS2	13		strip screening oxide; grow 15 nm SiO ₂ at 1000 °C; deposit 22 nm PECVD SiN _x	As	Si(100)
TS3	41		grow 15 nm SiO ₂ at 1000 °C; deposit 90 nm PECVD SiN _x	None	Si(111)
TS4	6		anneal at 900 °C for 10 min; leave 15 nm screening oxide; deposit 22 nm PECVD SiN _x ; etch oxide and PECVD SiN _x	Sb	Si(100)
TS5	43		grow thermal SiO ₂ only	None	Si(111)
TS6	44		grow thermal SiO ₂ ; perform a post-oxidation treatment for improved stability	None	Si(111)

3 Cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer

3.1 Updated facility

The UV spectral responsivity calibration and temporal stability assessment of the mentioned silicon photodiodes was conducted at a cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer (CESR) facility at PTB. CESRs are primary standards for the measurement of optical radiant power [1], and therefore provide SI-traceable calibration possibilities of radiation detectors' spectral responsivity $s(\lambda)$.

The PTB cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer [15, 16] comprises a radiant power absorber that is thermally coupled to a temperature-stabilized heat sink maintained slightly above the temperature of liquid helium. The absorber is electrically heated to a defined temperature slightly above that of the heat sink. When additional radiant power is absorbed, the electrical heating power must be reduced accordingly to keep the absorber at a constant temperature. This change in electrical heating power can be measured with low uncertainty and serves as a direct measure of the absorbed radiant power Φ_{CESR} , traceable to the PTB realizations of the electrical quantities voltage and resistance.

To prevent icing of the cavity due to water vapour in the air, the CESR is operated under vacuum. Since the rest of the measurement setup, such as the radiation sources and the detectors to be calibrated, is not operated under vacuum, an entrance window is required. This entrance window is made of fused silica and has a wedge angle of 3° to avoid interference effects.

A second, nominal identical wedged window is positioned in front of the detectors under

Figure 2: Typical radiant power at the CESR and the detector under test during calibration.

test to obtain a comparable beam path. Therefore, only the ratio F_{window} of the transmittances of the two nominal identical windows has to be measured for a correction of the spectral responsivity measurement at each calibration wavelength. The calibration took place at 25 °C laboratory and detector temperature, and a reverse bias voltage of 1 V was applied throughout.

A maximum of 3 detectors can be calibrated simultaneously against the CESR. A monitor photodiode is used to correct for temporal drifts in the radiant power level during the measurement process. The photocurrents of the monitor and detector under test are read out synchronously using two transimpedance amplifiers and two digital Agilent 3458A voltmeters. A shutter is used to correct for background signal drift.

Recently, this CESR facility at PTB was updated with a laser-driven light source (LDLS) of the type EQ-1500 from Energetiq Technology, Inc. as a broadband UV radiation source. Together with a prism and a grating monochromator combination, calibrations in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 410 nm with a spectral bandwidth of about 1 nm are enabled. The realized radiant power at the detector under test is depicted in Fig. 2.

3.2 Determination of the spectral responsivity

The spectral responsivity s_{meas} is determined according to Eq. 3. The quantities will be explained in the following.

$$s_{\text{meas}}(\lambda) = \frac{U_{\text{DUT}}}{R_{\text{TIA}}} \cdot \frac{U_{\text{Mon-CESR}}}{U_{\text{Mon-DUT}} \cdot \Phi_{\text{CESR}}} \cdot F \quad (3)$$

The photocurrent $I_{\text{ph,DUT}}$ of the detector under test (DUT) is measured as the voltage U_{DUT} with a transimpedance amplifier (TIA) with the feedback resistance R_{TIA} . Φ_{CESR} is the radiant power determined by the CESR.

The photocurrent of the monitor detector is measured as the voltage $U_{\text{Mon-DUT}}$ (synchronously measured with U_{DUT}) respectively $U_{\text{Mon-CESR}}$ (synchronously measured with Φ_{CESR}) with a second TIA. Its feedback resistance cancels out in Eq. 3, as $U_{\text{Mon-CESR}}$ and $U_{\text{Mon-DUT}}$ are measured with the same TIA. The correction factor F is the product of the following quantities, see also Tab. 4:

- F_{α} : Cavity absorptance of the CESR
- F_{window} : Wavelength dependent measured ratio of the window transmittances
- $F_{\Delta\lambda}$: Spectral bandwidth correction factor
- F_{O_2} : Correction factor due to oxygen absorption
- F_{SR} : Correction factor due to stray radiation
- F_{Φ} : Correction factor due to the electrical power measurement of the CESR

Figure 3: Typical relative standard measurement uncertainty, exemplarily shown for the first measurement with TS3.

- F_λ : Wavelength correction factor
- $F_{\text{non-uni}}$: Correction factor due to non-uniformity of the DUT’s spectral responsivity across the sensitive area and an uncertainty of the central detector position x_0 in the beam. Due to repeated detector positioning cycles, the estimated position uncertainty $u(x_0)$ is 0.2 mm. $u(F_{\text{non-uni}})$ is calculated by multiplying $u(x_0)$ by $\frac{\partial I_{\text{ph,rel}}}{\partial x}$, see Sect. 4.2.
- F_T : Correction factor due to temperature dependence of the DUT’s spectral responsivity

4 Measurement results

4.1 Measurement uncertainty

Firstly, the measurement uncertainty budget is presented in order to evaluate the UV spectral responsivity calibration and determine whether observed temporal instabilities are significant: In this publication, changes in spectral responsivity are considered insignificant when the absolute difference between repeated measurements does not exceed the standard measurement uncertainty of the individual measurements. A detector fulfilling this condition over the observation period is regarded as temporally stable.

The typical relative standard measurement uncertainty is exemplarily shown for the first measurement of TS3 in Fig. 3. It is in the order of 0.1 % for the wavelength range from 270 nm and above. Due to reduced radiant power below 270 nm, compare Fig. 2, the relative standard measurement uncertainty increases with shorter wavelengths up to about 0.8 %, since one of the major uncertainty contributions is type A uncertainty of the measured signals from the CESR and the detector under test. A full measurement uncertainty budget for two exemplarily chosen wavelengths is presented in Tab. 4.

4.2 Uniformity characterisation

The central detector position x_0 to which the detectors were aligned in the beam was found by scanning the detector in 0.5 mm steps and measuring the detector signal $I_{\text{ph}}(x)$ at each position x . These scans have been performed for all detector rotation angles at intervals of 30° . The obtained data provide information not only about the central detector position x_0 but also about the spatial distribution of the spectral responsivity across the detectors’ sensitive area, which is referred to here as ‘non-uniformity’. The beam has a wavelength-independent diameter of about 2.6 mm.

Figure 4: Relative measured detector signal $I_{\text{ph,rel}}$ in dependence of the detector position position x (blue). The red line depicts the linear fit $\frac{\partial I_{\text{ph,rel}}}{\partial x}$, corresponding to the values given in Tab. 3.

Tab. 3 lists the relative change of the detector signal $I_{\text{ph,rel}} = \frac{I_{\text{ph}}(x)}{I_{\text{ph,max}}}$ across the sensitive area. $\frac{\partial I_{\text{ph,rel}}}{\partial x}$ is calculated by applying a least square fit to the relative measured detector signals across the sensitive area. This fit is only performed on data points where the full beam is incident on the photodiodes and is not blocked by the aperture. If parabolic shapes appear in the detector signal scans that would lead to $\frac{\partial I_{\text{ph,rel}}}{\partial x_0} = 0$, the fit can be performed section-wise over data points $I_{\text{ph,rel}}(x)$ that follow a linear trend approximately. Fig. 4 shows exemplarily data for three of the detectors, which exhibit varying degrees of non-uniformity. The measurements were taken at 320 nm.

Due to poor uniformity of TS1 and TS4, these two detectors were excluded from the temporal stability assessment and will not be discussed here anymore. The remaining detectors, however, show excellent uniformity, where $u(F_{\text{non-uni}})$ is negligible.

Table 3: Non-uniformity of the detectors, given by the relative change of the detector signal across the sensitive area.

Detector name	$ \frac{\partial I_{\text{ph,rel}}}{\partial x} / \% \cdot \text{mm}^{-1}$
TC1	0.008
TC2	0.040
TC3	0.014
TC4	0.019
TS1	> 0.3
TS2	0.010
TS3	0.010
TS4	> 0.3
TS5	0.007
TS6	0.004

4.3 Spectral responsivity and its temporal stability

4.3.1 Spectral responsivity

Fig. 5 shows the spectral responsivity $s_{\text{meas}}(\lambda)$ as calibrated against the CESR for several of the set-up detectors and the spectral responsivity $s_{\text{calc}}(\lambda)$ according to Eq. 2 for the ideal case $\rho(\lambda) = \delta(\lambda) = 0$ and $y(\lambda) = 1$. The differences between $s_{\text{meas}}(\lambda)$ and $s_{\text{calc}}(\lambda)$, and the extent to which these can be explained by the simulation and measurement results of the

Figure 5: Measured spectral responsivity of the studied detectors and spectral responsivity of a so-called ideal photodiode with $s = e \cdot \lambda \cdot h^{-1} \cdot c^{-1}$, compare Eq. 2. For each detector, the first measurement performed as listed in Tab. 1 is shown. The measurement uncertainties are too small to be seen meaningfully, and are therefore not depicted, see Sect. 4.1.

photodiodes key parameters ρ , δ and y will be discussed comprehensively in [8]. The precise spectral responsivity calibrations allow the derived key parameters of the photodiodes to be validated independently. This validates whether the photodiodes can be used as primary detector standards.

However, it can be seen that TS2 and TS3 show almost identical spectral behaviour; as well as TS5 and TS6, which show almost identical spectral behaviour. Since TC1 to TC4 also show similar results with each other, only TC2 is depicted.

4.3.2 Temporal stability of TC1 to TC4

Fig. 6 shows a comparison of the spectral responsivity of detectors TC2 and TC3 over a time period of almost two years, with four consecutive measurements. Detector TC3 exhibits excellent stability within the relative standard measurements uncertainty of about 0.1% across all measurements. As the slight increase in spectral responsivity in the wavelength range from 300 nm to 350 nm in the third and fourth measurement compared to the first and second measurement occurs not only for TC3, but with almost identical spectral features also for TC4 and a well-known PTB reference detector which has been calibrated alongside as a cross-check, this increase is most likely due to a measurement artefact rather than due to temporal instability of the detectors' spectral responsivity. Note that the observed change is well within the stated measurement uncertainty. The results for TC1 and TC4 reveal almost identical temporal stability.

TC2's temporal stability in the wavelength range from 300 nm and above over the first three measurements is comparable to that of TC1, TC3 and TC4. Note that the third measurement in February 2026 was split into two: First, the spectral range 300 nm to 410 nm was measured, followed by the spectral range 200 nm to 300 nm. However, the fourth measurement in March 2026 revealed a significant degradation, not only in the spectral range 200 nm to 300 nm with a responsivity reduced by almost 25%, but also in the spectral range above 300 nm, which had previously been stable, by about 7%.

This instability of TC2 is most likely caused by irradiation from 200 nm to 280 nm in the second split of the third measurement. By considering $n = 3$ measurement repetitions at each wavelength (conducted at axial rotation angles 0° , 60° and 120°), estimating the exposure time $t = 4$ s and a beam diameter of $d = 2.6$ mm at the detector's sensitive area and using the known radiant power Φ_λ as shown in Fig. 2, the UV exposure H in the wavelength range

Figure 6: Comparison of the spectral responsivity over four consecutive measurements of detectors TC3 and TC2. For detector TC3, the relative deviation from the mean of all four measurements is shown. In contrast, for detector TC2, the relative deviation from the mean of the first three measurements is shown. The degradation of TC2 is most likely caused by irradiation in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 280 nm as outlined in Sect. 4.3.2.

200 nm to 280 nm can be approximated:

$$H = \sum_{\lambda=200 \text{ nm}}^{280 \text{ nm}} \frac{\Phi_{\lambda} \cdot t \cdot n}{\frac{\pi}{4} d^2} \approx 6.2 \text{ mJ} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \quad (4)$$

The degradation of silicon photodiodes due to UV irradiation is a well-known phenomenon [10, 11, 17]. Getz et al. provide an in-depth study of the UV stability of photodiodes in the chipS-CALe and S-CALe Up projects [14].

4.3.3 Temporal stability of TS2, TS3 and TS6

Fig. 7 shows a comparison of the spectral responsivity of detectors TS2, TS3 and TS6 over two consecutive measurements.

The spectral responsivity of detector TS2 shows a slight decrease at wavelengths equal to or longer than 220 nm, ranging from about 0.1% to 0.3%. This is significant compared to the relative standard measurement uncertainty realized in this wavelength range. Below 220 nm, the spectral responsivity differs more strongly between the two measurements, with both increased and decreased values measured. This scattering can most probably be explained by higher measurement uncertainty in this spectral range, compare Fig. 3. Overall, therefore, a slight degradation in the spectral responsivity of TS2 can be observed.

In contrast, TS3 shows a clear increase in spectral responsivity in the spectral range below 280 nm, up to about 1%. From 280 nm and above, the spectral responsivity remains stable within the realised measurement uncertainty.

The same applies to TS6 for the entire studied spectral range. Its spectral responsivity remains stable at around 0.1% to 0.2%.

Figure 7: Comparison of the spectral responsivity over each two consecutive measurements with detectors TS2, TS3 and TS6. The relative deviation of the second from the first measurement is shown.

However, the interval between the first and second measurement was short for TS2, TS3 and TS6. Therefore, a more thorough assessment of temporal stability should be considered in future.

5 Conclusion

Several three-element reflection trap detectors with silicon photodiodes which were produced in the chipS-CALe and S-CALe Up projects have been set-up. Most of the photodiodes are so-called induced-junction photodiodes with reduced recombination losses, meant to serve as primary detector standards, so called Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQEDs).

These detectors have been calibrated in view of their spectral responsivity in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 410 nm against a cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer (CESR) facility at the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB). PTB has recently updated this facility with a laser-driven light source for SI-traceable detector calibrations of the spectral responsivity in the UV wavelength range down to 200 nm.

- A comprehensive measurement uncertainty budget is presented, with typical relative standard measurement uncertainties in the range of about 0.1%. These highly accurate measurements have been performed in order to investigate the temporal stability of the photodiodes' spectral responsivity.
- It is revealed, that photodiodes produced in the chipS-CALe project are temporally stable in the wavelength range 280 nm to 410 nm within in the realised measurement uncertainty over a time frame of about 2 years.
- There is one induced-junction photodiode candidate (Wafer 44, see Tab. 1) among the photodiodes produced in the S-CALe Up project, which shows temporally stable spectral responsivity in the full spectral range 200 nm to 410 nm within the measurement uncertainty. However, this temporal stability was limited to a time period of two months; a more extended study should be considered.

To place the present results in context, long-term calibrations at PTB of three-element reflection trap detectors equipped with Hamamatsu S1337-1010 silicon photodiodes show a mean annual decrease in spectral responsivity of approximately 0.2% in the wavelength range from 220 nm to 370 nm. The photodiodes investigated here therefore exhibit very good temporal stability by comparison.

Furthermore, these precise calibrations of the spectral responsivity s_{meas} allow the derived key parameters of the photodiodes to be validated independently by comparing s_{meas} to the calculated spectral responsivity s_{calc} according to Eq. 2 for the first time in the UV spectral range [8].

Acknowledgements

The project 22IEM06 S-CALe Up has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, methodology and supervision: all authors; Photodiode development and fabrication: O.K., M.N.G; Photodiode packaging: E.B.; Detector housing design and setup: T.P.; Data acquisition and analysis: P.M., T.P., L.W.; Original manuscript: T.P., P.M.; Manuscript contributions: L.W., O.K., M.N.G., M.-M.S., J.G.; Project administration: J.G., L.W., T.P.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

References

- [1] J. E. Martin, N. P. Fox, and P. J. Key. A cryogenic radiometer for absolute radiometric measurements. *Metrologia*, 21(3):147, 1985.
- [2] Mikhail Korpusenko, Anna Vaskuri, Farshid Manoocheri1, and Erkki Ikonen. Internal quantum efficiency of silicon photodetectors at ultraviolet wavelengths. *Metrologia*, 60(5):055010, 2023.
- [3] chipS-CALe - EURAMET European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) project 18SIB10. <http://chipscale.aalto.fi/>. Accessed: 2026-05-29.
- [4] S-CALe Up - EURAMET European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) project 22IEM06. <https://scaleup.aalto.fi/>. Accessed: 2026-05-29.
- [5] Trinh Tran, Lutz Werner, Ulrike Linke, and Jarle Gran. 3D simulation of internal recombination losses of silicon chipscale photodiode in UV range. *Newrad Conference*, 2026.
- [6] Trinh Tran et al. Simulation of spectral responsivity of predictable quantum efficient detector based on induced-junction photodiodes passivated with SiO₂/SiN_x (to be published), 2026.

- [7] Meelis-Mait Sildoja, Mauro Rajteri, Aarre Kilpeläinen, Farshid Manoocheri, and Erkki Ikonen. Reflectance modelling of trap detectors consisting of induced junction photodiodes at wavelengths between 200-450 nm. Newrad Conference, 2026.
- [8] Toomas Kübarsepp, Meelis-Mait Sildoja, Jaanus Vahi, Aarre Kilpeläinen, Farshid Manoocheri, Peter Meindl, Tobias Pohl, Lutz Werner, Marek Šmid, Geiland Porrovecchio, Trinh Tran, Jarle Gran, and Erkki Ikonen. Quantum yield of silicon in the near uv spectral range (to be published). Metrologia, xx(x):xx, 2026.
- [9] Lutz Werner, Ulrike Linke, Ingmar Müller, Toomas Kubarsepp, Meelis-Mait Sildoja, Trinh Tran, and Jarle Gran. Quantum yield in induced-junction silicon photodiodes at wavelengths around 400 nm. Metrologia, 61(3):035002, 2024.
- [10] G. Porrovecchio, U. Linke, M. Smid, J. Gran, E. Ikonen, and L. Werner. Long-term spectral responsivity stability of predictable quantum efficient detectors. Metrologia, 59(6):065008, 2022.
- [11] Lutz Werner, Joachim Fischer, Uwe Johannsen, and Jürgen Hartmann. Accurate determination of the spectral responsivity of silicon trap detectors between 238 nm and 1015 nm using a laser-based cryogenic radiometer. Metrologia, 37(4):279, 2000.
- [12] N. P. Fox. Trap detectors and their properties. Metrologia, 28(3):197, 1991.
- [13] Ozhan Koybasi, Ørnulf Nordseth, Trinh Tran, Marco Povoli, Mauro Rajteri, Carlo Pepe, Eivind Bardalen, Farshid Manoocheri, Anand Summanwar, Mikhail Korpusenko, Michael Getz, Per Ohlckers, Erkki Ikonen, and Jarle Gran. High performance predictable quantum efficient detector based on induced-junction photodiodes passivated with SiO₂/SiN_x. Sensors, 21(23):7807, 2021.
- [14] Michael N. Getz, Ozhan Koybasi, Fredrik Edhborg, Ørnulf Nordseth, Steven Hesse, Tobias Pohl, Marco Povoli, Stefan Källberg, Lutz Werner, Erkki Ikonen, and Jarle Gran. Improving UV stability of SiO₂/SiN_x-passivated silicon photodiodes through shallow junction implantation and oxide regrowth (to be published). Sensors, xx(xx):xx, 2026.
- [15] Peter Meindl, Andreas Klinkmueller, Lutz Werner, Uwe Johannsen, and K. Gruetzmacher. New UV spectral responsivity scale of the PTB based on a cryogenic radiometer and an argon plasma arc radiation source. Metrologia, 43(2):72, 2006.
- [16] Tobias Pohl, Peter Meindl, Uwe Johannsen, Dieter Taubert, and Lutz Werner. Measurement of the absolute spectral responsivity in the mid-infrared based on the cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer and an optimized thermopile detector. J. Sens. Sens. Syst., 8(1):195–205, 2019.
- [17] Aarre Kilpeläinen, Farshid Manoocheri, Fredrik Edhborg, Stefan Källberg, Ozhan Koybasi, Eivind Bardalen, Lutz Werner, Jarle Gran, and Erkki Ikonen. Degradation characterization of induced junction photodiodes under ultraviolet irradiation. Metrologia, 63(2), 2026.

Table 4: Measurement uncertainty budget for the first calibration of TS3 at 205 nm and 330 nm. Standard uncertainties in normal distribution are listed. $u_{\text{rel}}(x_i)$ is the relative contribution of x_i according to $\frac{\frac{\partial s}{\partial x_i} \cdot u(x_i)}{s(\lambda)}$.

X_i	$\lambda = 205 \text{ nm}$				$\lambda = 330 \text{ nm}$			
	x_i	$u(x_i)$	$ \frac{\partial s}{\partial x_i} \cdot u(x_i) / \frac{\text{A}}{\text{W}}$	$u_{\text{rel}}(x_i) / \%$	x_i	$u(x_i)$	$ \frac{\partial s}{\partial x_i} \cdot u(x_i) / \frac{\text{A}}{\text{W}}$	$u_{\text{rel}}(x_i) / \%$
Φ_{CESR}	0.3960 W	0.0004 W	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.11	4.4758 W	0.0010 W	$5.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.02
U_{DUT}	0.1501 V	0.0003 V	$7.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.19	11.8863 V	0.0075 V	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.06
$U_{\text{Mon-DUT}}$	0.0197 V	$< 0.0001 \text{ V}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01	0.2733 V	$< 0.0001 \text{ V}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01
$U_{\text{Mon-CESR}}$	0.0197 V	$< 0.0001 \text{ V}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01	0.2726 V	$< 0.0001 \text{ V}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01
R_{TIA}	$9.989 \cdot 10^6 \Omega$	$5.7 \cdot 10^3 \Omega$	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.06	$9.989 \cdot 10^6 \Omega$	$5.7 \cdot 10^3 \Omega$	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.06
F_{α}	0.9998	< 0.0001	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01	0.9998	< 0.0001	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01
F_{window}	0.9988	0.0005	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.05	0.9994	0.0003	$8.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.03
$F_{\Delta\lambda}$	0.9997	0.0001	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.01	1.0000	0.0001	$2.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.01
F_{O_2}	1.0015	0.0003	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.03	1.0000	< 0.0001	$< 0.1 \cdot 10^{-8}$	< 0.01
F_{SR}	1	0.0004	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.04	1	0.0004	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.04
F_{ϕ}	1	0.0002	$5.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.02	1	0.0002	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.02
F_{λ}	0.9969	0.0038	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.38	1.0000	0.0001	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.01
$F_{\text{non-uni}}$	1	< 0.0001	$7.6 \cdot 10^{-7}$	< 0.01	1	< 0.0001	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01
F_T	1	0.0001	$4.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.01	1	< 0.0001	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	< 0.01
$u_{\text{c,rel}}(s(\lambda)) / \%$	0.45				0.10			

2.5 Presentation 1: W44 – SCALe Up photodiode

W44 – SCALe Up
photodiode

Photodiode structure

The same as chips.cale photodiodes except that the dielectric is thermal SiO₂ instead of SiO₂/SiN_x. The thickness of SiO₂ is 300 nm.

Parameters	Values
Qf	3.7e11
SRV	5000
Doping	2.4e12
lifetime	1 ms

Uncertainty

Best fit is black curve-
simulation at 300 μ W

Spectral responsivity

Wavelength nm	IQD/ppm Best fit	IQD/ppm Lower curve	IQD/ppm Upper curve
200	669.2	2882.5	370.6
250	634.3	2755.9	349.5
300	635.3	2748.4	350.7
350	553.9	2415.5	303.6
400	162.6	695.2	88.3
450	71.5	281.7	40.1
500	46.6	170.0	27.0
647	24.4	75.6	14.9

2.6 Report 1: Reflectance of ChipS-CALe and S-CALe UP photodiodes at wavelengths between 200-500 nm: measurements, modelling and uncertainty

Reflectance of ChipS-CALe and S-CALe UP photodiodes at wavelengths between 200-500 nm: measurements, modelling and uncertainty

1. Introduction

The reflectance modelling of photodiodes produced in ChipS-CALe and S-CALe UP projects are reported for single photodiodes and for 3-element trap detectors. Target wavelength range of the modelling was 200-500 nm. The model output has been compared and fitted with the measurements to improve the accuracy of the model using fine-tuning of the input parameters of the model. A thorough uncertainty analysis of is provided.

2. Model

Reflectance loss from one element is calculated based on transfer-matrix method for multiple thin films [1] (Figure 1a). For 3-element trap detector the total reflectance is combined from 5 consecutive reflections of single elements as shown in Figure 1b. As input parameters, the model needs polarization state and incidence angle of the radiation and thickness and material parameters (index of refraction and absorption coefficient) of each thin layer and substrate at each wavelength. For 3-element trap detector combined reflectance the model takes into account subsequent reflections at different angles and polarization states.

For the calculations an extensive MATLAB code has been developed.

Figure 1. a) formation of reflected and absorbed irradiation due to multiple reflections in thin layer on top of bulk substrate; b) beam path in 3-element trap detector.

3. S-CALe UP photodiode reflectance modelling

From several photodiodes produced in the project the most promising ones were chosen for further studies. These photodiodes were originating from wafer W44 and consisted of chips with thick SiO₂ layer on top of bulk silicon. In the reflectance model a more detailed structure was used including the naturally occurring layers of surface roughness on top SiO₂ and the thin interface layer between Si and SiO₂ [2-8] (Figure 2). These layers have minor effects at visible wavelengths, but noticeable effects at short UV wavelengths at around 200-300 nm.

Nevertheless, the surface roughness is not considered in reflectance analysis as variable, but it is fixed at its nominal value. This is because its thickness would have to vary 10-fold over its nominal value to have similar effect as sub-nanometer interface layer. No study has confirmed that such thick roughness would ever form on top of SiO₂ layer.

Surface roughness, <1 nm
SiO ₂ , ~300nm
SiO ₂ /Si mixture layer, ~1 nm
Si substrate, ~500 μm

Figure 2. Layered structure of the W44 photodiode.

Initial nominal thickness of SiO₂ layer (300 nm) was provided by the manufacturer (SINTEF), the approximate thicknesses of thin natural layers of surface roughness (< 1 nm) and interface layer (~1 nm) are known from the literature and were also confirmed by the manufacturer. For more detailed information about the surface roughness and interface thickness and their material parameters see the uncertainty evaluation paragraph. The determination of exact layer thicknesses and verification of the reflectance model was made in several steps. In first stage single photodiodes were studied using both ellipsometer and dedicated reflectometric facilities. Measurements with ellipsometer were carried out at INRIM. The obtained layer thicknesses are expected to be sufficiently accurate and allow estimate also multi-element trap reflectance with sufficient uncertainty. Reflectance measurements of single photodiodes were conducted at TUBITAK and CSIC using spectrophotometer and custom-built monochromator-based reflectometers. These measurements were conducted at multiple angles (7°/8°, 15°, 30°, 45°), polarizations (s-pol, p-pol) and wavelengths (300 – 800 nm) to fit the layer thicknesses and compare the outcome with the model. The obtained layer thicknesses had larger variation than those obtained with ellipsometer but provided valuable information about the reflectance measurement technique suitability for layer thickness determination. Empirically one can say that reflectance measurements carried out at larger incident angles (45°) gave better agreement with ellipsometer measurements in respect of layer thickness similarity. In addition, the samples used for measurements were originating from different sections of the wafer thus variation in layer thicknesses was expected. In the second phase the reflectance model was compared and fitted with laser-based measurements of 3-element trap detector. This allowed layer thicknesses to be determined (for the specific photodiodes) with significantly improved uncertainty due to low uncertainty of the highly monochromatic laser-based measurements and multiple reflections (5 in total) in the trap detector. The latter has effect in the parameter sensitivity in reflectance model. Fractional change in any layer thickness has relatively large effect in trap reflectance which is about 5-fold larger as compared to that of single photodiode. Reflectance could thus be predicted with lower uncertainty. The trap reflectance measurements were conducted at Aalto University.

3.1 Single photodiode measurements and modelling

3.1.1 Measurements at INRIM

Table 1. Obtained layer thicknesses using ellipsometer.

Surface roughness	0.22 nm
SiO ₂	292.14 nm
Interface layer between Si/SiO ₂	0.76 nm

3.1.2 Modelling based on CSIC measurements

Reflectance model fitting with measured data obtained at CSIC with PerkinElmer Lambda900 spectrophotometer showed systematic mismatch between *s*-pol and *p*-pol cases. It was concluded that the *s*-pol radiation may contain fractional *p*-pol component during measurements or there is other systematic offset in the data. It is clearly seen that thickness values obtained at *s*-pol and *p*-pol radiation differ from each other at all measurement angles. Extremely high values of surface roughness at *s*-pol show systematic deviation from expected value when fitting the data. Even at *p*-pol the roughness exceeds the expected value which is below 1 nm [6-7].

Table 2. Obtained layer thicknesses based on CSIC measurements with PerkinElmer Lambda900.

Angle of incidence	Polarization	Surface roughness (nm)	SiO ₂ (nm)	Interface Si/SiO ₂ (nm)
45 deg	<i>s</i>	16.1	288.9	1.7
	<i>p</i>	1.1	295.7	0.9
30 deg	<i>s</i>	15.4	288.8	1.7
	<i>p</i>	6.1	294.0	0.6
15 deg	<i>s</i>	15.0	289.1	1.7
	<i>p</i>	6.1	293.9	0.2
8 deg	<i>s</i>	13.1	289.5	1.7
	<i>p</i>	9.6	291.4	0.9
Average		10.3	291.4	1.2
STDEV		5.5	2.8	0.6

Obtained thicknesses if only *p*-pol data is used for analysis.

	Polarization	Surface roughness (nm)	SiO ₂ (nm)	Interface Si/SiO ₂ (nm)
Average	<i>p</i>-pol	4.5	293.7	0.8
STDEV	<i>p</i>-pol	0.8	1.8	0.2

Figure 3. Reflectance measurements at *s*- and *p*-pol radiation at 45-deg angle using PerkinElmer Lambda900 and fitting curves using *p*-pol data. Measured sample was photodiode from wafer W44.

3.1.3 Modelling based on TUBITAK measurements

Layer thickness values obtained by fitting the model to measured data conducted with monochromator-based facility at TUBITAK indicated no systematic variations between *s*- and *p*-pol radiation. On the other hand, best fit conditions were achieved very often at exceptionally high surface roughness values indicating some other systematic effect in the measured data. See Table 3. In addition there is one clear outlier with oxide thickness $d_{\text{SiO}_2} = 298.2$ nm obtained at 15° *p*-pol measurements.

Table 3. Obtained layer thicknesses by fitting reflectance model with TUBITAK measurements carried out in monochromator-based facility.

Angle of incidence	Polarization	Surface roughness (nm)	SiO ₂ (nm)	Interface Si/SiO ₂ (nm)
45 deg	<i>s</i>	2.2	293.8	1.0
	<i>p</i>	9.3	291.2	1.9
30 deg	<i>s</i>	9.3	291.6	0.4
	<i>p</i>	12.5	289.6	1.5
15 deg	<i>s</i>	8.1	291.6	0.9
	<i>p</i>	1.1	298.2	1.1
8 deg	<i>s</i>	9.0	291.6	0.7
	<i>p</i>	10.9	289.8	1.9
Average		7.8	292.2	1.2
STDEV		4.0	2.8	0.5

Figure 4 shows an example of measured reflectance and model fitting quality at 45° . The model is fitted using *p*-pol data only. It is seen that with the obtained layer thicknesses also the *s*-pol data fits well with measurements, but according to Table 3 the best fit with *s*-pol data is achieved at significantly different layer thicknesses. This indicates that slight variation in the measured data (inaccuracy in the measurements) results significant variation in obtained layer thicknesses yielding single photodiode reflectance measurements a poor source if high-accurate reflectance modelling.

Figure 4. Reflectance measurements at *p*- and *s*-pol radiation at 45-deg angle using monochromator-based facility at TUBUTAK and fitting curves using *p*-pol data. Measured sample was photodiode from wafer W44.

3.2 Modelling based on trap detector measurements

3.2.1 Measurements at AALTO

Reflectance of a 3-element trap detector with S-CALe UP W44 photodiodes was measured at laser lines of 325 nm, 405 nm and 442 nm at Aalto University. Reflectance modelling and fitting using trap-based measurements yielded significant improvement in the estimation of layer thicknesses and as a result also modelling accuracy. Detailed overview is given in the uncertainty section.

Table 5. Measured reflectances of 3-element W44 trap detector.

Wavelength	Reflectance
325 nm	0.5290% with 1.1% relative standard uncertainty
405 nm	1.5596% with 0.8% relative standard uncertainty
442 nm	0.2722% with 2.1% relative standard uncertainty

3.2.2 Parameters and their uncertainties affecting reflectance modelling when using laser-based measurements of trap detector

Layer thicknesses

Nominal value for SiO₂ layer thickness has been determined using ellipsometer. Interface layer thickness has lot of controversy in the literature varying from 0 nm to few nanometers [2-8]. For thin SiO₂ layer below 10 nm the Si/SiO₂ interface layer seems to be in the order of 0.1 nm or less. For thermally grown thick Si oxide the interface layer is between 0.5-1 nm [3-8] with mostly reported value to be around 0.6 nm. This range is confirmed also with our modelling. Surface

roughness is estimated by private communication with Si wafer process engineers and supported by the values reported in literature [7-8].

Material parameters

Index of refraction for thermally grown SiO₂ layer is obtained from [8]. An independent investigation [9] has confirmed that the reported values in [8] are in good agreement with experiments at all visible wavelengths down to 300 nm, where gradual increase in difference is observed peaking at 200 nm with relative difference of 0.15% in $n(\text{SiO}_2)$. The effect of this difference is included in the uncertainty analysis when considering the optical thickness ($d_o = d * n$, where d = layer thickness, n = index of refraction) values of SiO₂.

Material parameters (index of refraction) for interface layer and for surface roughness are estimated using the Bruggeman effective media approximation (EMA) [8,10]. Values for interface layer are readily available in [8] whereas for surface roughness they were calculated assuming 50% material mixing ratio in volume and taking the surrounding air index of refraction equal to 1. Material parameters (index of refraction and absorption coefficient) for silicon are obtained from [8]. Herzinger [8] does not provide any uncertainty estimation for the reported values, but Green [11] has extensively studied both $n(\text{Si})$ and $k(\text{Si})$ values reported on several sources, including Herzinger [8], and gives an estimation on these parameters' accuracy. He's analysis is taken as basis for the uncertainties for n and k of Si. Numerical values from Green's [11] research are based on the following quote: "Error limits on tabulated k and a are estimated to increase from $\pm 0.3\%$ at $0.25 \mu\text{m}$ to $\pm 4\%$ beyond $0.46 \mu\text{m}$, $\pm 10\%$ beyond $1.2 \mu\text{m}$ and to become even larger beyond $1.4 \mu\text{m}$. For n , estimated accuracy is better than $\pm 0.1\%$ beyond $1.0 \mu\text{m}$, increasing to about $\pm 0.5\%$ at shorter λ except below $0.3 \mu\text{m}$ where it increases to $\pm 1\%$." Here it is assumed that reported error limits are equivalent with expanded standard uncertainty ($k=2$).

Figure 5. Uncertainty profiles of $n(\text{Si})$ and $k(\text{Si})$ based on ref [11].

Uncertainty analysis

Starting point of the uncertainty analysis was first to find best fit between measured and modelled reflectances using nominal material parameters for bulk Si and for each thin layer and by changing the interface layer, oxide layer and surface roughness thicknesses at the vicinity of their nominal values so that modelled values at 325 nm, 405 nm and 442 nm would agree with measured reflectances at same wavelengths. The obtained best fit thicknesses were taken as the new nominal values. This analysis gave also the information about the thickness sensitivities of

each layer to the reflectance. See Table 6. Based on that study the surface roughness variation has minor effect on reflectance. As roughness is known to have small but still non-zero value, it was fixed at 0.25 nm which agrees also in report [7]. The best fit interface layer with 0.88 nm agrees also well with previously reported values [3-7]. The best fit oxide layer turned out to be 292.17 nm. Interface and oxide layers contribute significantly into reflectance change when varied. The magnitudes of these changes are different at different wavelengths but similar in shape. To estimate the reflectance uncertainty due to layer thickness uncertainties, both layers were varied simultaneously so that resulting reflectance would go through the measured reflectance uncertainty low limits and high limits as closely as possible.

Another effect to consider, is that all three diodes may have slightly different oxide layer thicknesses. Calculations indicate that last (3rd) photodiode's contribution into total reflectance is significantly smaller than that of the first two diodes. Considering this aspect, reflectance variation was studied so that the oxide thicknesses of the first and the second photodiode were given slightly different values with maximum difference of 0.5 nm. This variation introduced also polarization sensitivity on the reflectance. Modelling on the other hand showed that such oxide layer variation produces poor match with measured reflectances indicating that all the photodiodes in the trap had very similar or equal layer structures. Based on that outcome no further studies and uncertainty analysis was carried out on the case of unequal oxide layers.

Table 6 describes the model parameters and their effect on reflectance modelling. Major effect means that the knowledge we have about the parameter with its uncertainty, has significant effect on the uncertainty in reflectance.

Table 6. Parameters and their significance affecting the reflectance modelling.

Layer thicknesses	Sensitivity on reflectance
SiO ₂	Major effect
Interface layer between Si and SiO ₂	Major effect at short UV
Surface roughness	Minor effect
Material parameters (index of refraction)	
n(Si)	Major effect
n(SiO ₂)	Minor effect
n(SiO ₂ /Si interface)	Minor effect
Material parameters (absorption coefficient)	
k(Si)	Major effect at short UV
k(SiO ₂) = 0	No effect
k(SiO ₂ /Si interface) = 0	No effect

Table 7. Obtained layer thicknesses used to estimate the effect on the reflectance uncertainty.

	Nominal values	Low values*	High values*
Surface roughness (fixed)	0.25 nm	0.25 nm	0.25 nm
Oxide thickness	292.17 nm	291.44 nm	292.93 nm
Interface layer thickness	0.88 nm	1.22 nm	0.51 nm

* Low and high values indicate for layer thicknesses which force the modelled reflectance to go through low and high uncertainty limits of the measured reflectances.

The effect of the material parameters on the uncertainty of reflectance was estimated in such a way that first the n(Si) was adjusted to its high values based on the uncertainty estimation given

in [11]. These values were taken as new nominal index of refractions of Si. After such variation the model was fitted (by finding new best fitting layer thicknesses) so that resulting reflectance would go through the measured reflectance values at 325 nm, at 405 nm and at 442 nm as closely as possible. Similar steps were carried out for the case where $n(\text{Si})$ was adjusted to its low values. The resulting two modelled reflectance graphs indicated the high and low uncertainty limits of reflectance due to uncertainty of $n(\text{Si})$.

Analogous procedures were performed to estimate the effect due to the uncertainty of $k(\text{Si})$ on the reflectance.

Table 8. Layer thicknesses used to estimate the effect on the reflectance uncertainty if $n(\text{Si})$ and $k(\text{Si})$ are adjusted to their new “nominal” values.

	$n(\text{Si}) = n(\text{Si})_{\text{nom}} - n(\text{Si})_{\text{unc}}$	$n(\text{Si}) = n(\text{Si})_{\text{nom}} + n(\text{Si})_{\text{unc}}$	$k(\text{Si}) = k(\text{Si})_{\text{nom}} - k(\text{Si})_{\text{unc}}$	$k(\text{Si}) = k(\text{Si})_{\text{nom}} + k(\text{Si})_{\text{unc}}$
Surface roughness	0.25 nm	0.25 nm	0.25 nm	0.25 nm
Oxide thickness	293.35 nm	291.16 nm	292.54 nm	291.88 nm
Interface layer thickness	0.04 nm	1.58 nm	0.42 nm	1.27 nm

The effect of index of refraction uncertainty of the interface layer is insignificant and was not included in the analysis.

The combined standard uncertainty is estimated using the obtained individual parameter uncertainty corridors (Figures 6-14) so that the differences from nominal reflectance are combined using square root of squared sums in a manner that for the final low uncertainty only negative difference values are considered and for the final high uncertainty only positive difference values are considered.

Uncertainty figures

Figure 6. Uncertainty corridors if layer thicknesses are varied according to Table 7.

Figure 7. Uncertainty limits if layer thicknesses are varied according to Table 7.

Figure 8. Uncertainty corridors if $n(\text{Si})$ is varied according to uncertainty analysis described in the text.

Figure 9. Uncertainty limits if $n(\text{Si})$ is varied according to uncertainty analysis described in the text.

Figure 10. Uncertainty corridors if $k(\text{Si})$ is varied according to uncertainty analysis described in the text.

Figure 11. Uncertainty limits if $k(\text{Si})$ is varied according to uncertainty analysis described in the text.

Figure 12. Reflectance with combined standard uncertainty corridors.

Figure 13. Combined standard uncertainty of 3-element S-CAL-e UP W44 trap reflectance.

Figure 14. Magnified sections of combined standard uncertainties at the vicinities of a) 325 nm, b) 405 nm and c) 442 nm respectively.

Figure 14 (c) shows that model fitting with the measurements cannot be accurately achieved for all measured data points simultaneously. This indicates that measurement at 442 nm (or possibly also at 325 nm or 405 nm) may have an unknown offset and/or the used material parameters used in model have inaccuracies. It may also be that the measurement uncertainty has been estimated too optimistically, which forbids fitting uncertainty to stay inside the measurement uncertainty limits. If one of the measured points are left out during fitting, then excellent agreement between measured and modelled values can be achieved but this on the other hand discards valuable information.

4. ChipS·CALe photodiode reflectance modelling

Similar approach to study ChipS·CALe 3-element trap reflectance was conducted as for S-CALe UP trap detector with some variations as the available data, both based on measurements and on literature, was limited as compared to W44 photodiode which has single oxide layer.

Surface roughness, ~1 nm
SiN _x , ~66 nm
SiO ₂ , ~6 nm
SiO ₂ /Si mixture layer, <1 nm
Si substrate, ~500 μm

Figure 15. Layered structure of the ChipS·CALe photodiode.

Ellipsometer measurements at INRIM gave the initial layer thicknesses and the material parameters for SiN_x layer. See table 9. Based on this data, initial modelling was performed and compared to single photodiode measurements conducted at CSIC and TUBITAK. This had somewhat controversial outcome. Model fitting into measured reflectance data had poor agreement and resulted also large variations in layer thicknesses between two institutes and also with the outcome of ellipsometer values. This may be explained by the fact that the chips used for measurements at each institute originated from different wafer indicating wafer-to-wafer parameter mismatch. Therefore thorough analysis was not carried out based on single photodiode measurements and further study was concentrated on trap reflectance modelling and fitting the model parameters to achieve agreement with reflectance measurements.

4.1 Single photodiode measurements

4.1.1 Ellipsometer measurements at INRIM

Table 9. Obtained layer thicknesses using ellipsometer.

Surface roughness	4.429 nm
SiN _x	66.47
SiO ₂	6.02 nm
Interface layer between Si/SiO ₂	0.0 nm

4.2 Trap detector modelling and measurements

4.2.1 Measurements at AALTO

Table 10. Measured reflectances of 3-element ChipS·CALe trap detector.

Wavelength	Reflectance
325 nm	4.872% with 1% relative uncertainty
405 nm	0.03575% with 2% relative uncertainty

4.2.2 Reflectance modelling and uncertainty analysis

Uncertainty analysis was performed similarly as for S-CALe UP trap detector but without the study of the SiN_x material parameter's effect on uncertainty as there was no reliable uncertainty

estimation for this data. For this reason, the given uncertainty of the reflectance model may be underestimated. As seen from the Figure 17 the obtained combined standard uncertainty is about factor of two smaller as given for ScaleUP trap detector. Small uncertainty can be explained also with the phenomenon that several layers of the photodiode with different material parameters and different thicknesses produce, when comparing with measurements, matching reflectance only under very strict conditions leaving small margin for parameter's variation.

Table 11. Obtained layer thicknesses used to estimate the effect on the reflectance uncertainty.

	Nominal values	Low values*	High values*
Surface roughness	3.35 nm	0.25 nm	0.25 nm
SiNx thickness	66.34 nm	291.44 nm	292.93 nm
SiO ₂ thickness	6.64 nm	1.22 nm	0.51 nm
Interface layer between Si/SiO ₂	0.11 nm	1.11 nm	0 nm

* Low and high values indicate for these layer thicknesses which force the modelled reflectance to go through low and high uncertainty limits of the measured reflectances.

Figure 16. ChipS-CALe 3-element trap modelled reflectance with combined standard uncertainty corridors. Black dots indicate measured reflectances.

Figure 17. Combined standard uncertainty of 3-element ChipS-CALe trap modelled reflectance.

Figure 18. Magnified sections of combined standard uncertainties of ChipS-CALe 3-element trap detector modelled reflectance at the vicinities of a) 325 nm and b) 405 nm.

References

- [1] Macleod H A 2001 Thin-Film Optical Filters (Institute of Physics Publishing)
- [2] Nguyen, N. V., Chandler-Horowitz, D., Amirtharaj, P. M. & Pellegrino, J. G. Spectroscopic ellipsometry determination of the properties of the thin underlying strained Si layer and the roughness at SiO₂/Si interface. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **64**, 2688–2690 (1994).
- [3] Aspnes, D. E. & Theeten, J. B. Optical Properties of the Interface between Si and Its Thermally Grown Oxide. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **43**, 1046–1050 (1979).
- [4] Johannessen, J. S. & Strausser, Y. E. An Auger analysis of the SiO₂-Si interface. *J. Appl. Phys.* **47**, 10 (1976).
- [5] Queeney, K. T. *et al.* Infrared spectroscopic analysis of the Si/SiO₂ interface structure of thermally oxidized silicon. *Journal of Applied Physics* **87**, 1322–1330 (2000).
- [6] Iacona, F., Raineri, V., La Via, F. & Rimini, E. Roughness of thermal oxide layers grown on ion implanted silicon wafers. *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology B: Microelectronics and Nanometer Structures Processing, Measurement, and Phenomena* **16**, 619–627 (1998).
- [7] Ohsawa, K., Hayashi, Y., Hasunuma, R. & Yamabe, K. Roughness increase on surface and interface of SiO₂ grown on atomically flat Si (111) terrace. *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **191**, 012031 (2009).
- [8] Herzinger, C. M., Johs, B., McGahan, W. A., Woollam, J. A. & Paulson, W. Ellipsometric determination of optical constants for silicon and thermally grown silicon dioxide via a multi-sample, multi-wavelength, multi-angle investigation. *Journal of Applied Physics* **83**, 3323–3336 (1998).
- [9] Rastgou, M. *et al.* Comparison of thin-film thickness measurements using ellipsometry and reflectometry with uniform samples. *Metrologia* **63**, 015006 (2026).
- [10] Bruggeman G 1935 Calculation of various physics constants in heterogeneous substances: I. Dielectricity constants and conductivity of mixed bodies from isotropic substances *Ann. Phys.* **416** 636
- [11] Green, M. A. Self-consistent optical parameters of intrinsic silicon at 300K including temperature coefficients. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* **92**, 1305–1310 (2008).

Tabulated data of ChipS·CALe and S-CALe UP (W44) 3-element trap reflectances with standard uncertainties.

3-element ChipS·CALe trap reflectance		Based on standard uncertainty, $k=1$; low limit = nominal refl - standard uncertainty	Based on standard uncertainty, $k=1$; high limit = nominal refl + standard uncertainty
Wavelength (nm)	Nominal reflectance (%)	Low reflectance limit (%)	High reflectance limit (%)
200	0.0812	0.0697	0.0938
201	0.0762	0.0647	0.0886
202	0.0709	0.0597	0.0830
203	0.0655	0.0546	0.0772
204	0.0603	0.0497	0.0714
205	0.0552	0.0451	0.0658
206	0.0466	0.0376	0.0560
207	0.0389	0.0310	0.0471
208	0.0321	0.0253	0.0391
209	0.0262	0.0204	0.0321
210	0.0212	0.0164	0.0261
211	0.0157	0.0120	0.0195
212	0.0115	0.0086	0.0143
213	0.0082	0.0061	0.0103
214	0.0057	0.0042	0.0072
215	0.0039	0.0028	0.0049
216	0.0024	0.0017	0.0030
217	0.0014	0.0010	0.0018
218	0.0008	0.0005	0.0010
219	0.0004	0.0003	0.0005
220	0.0002	0.0002	0.0003
221	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
222	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
223	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
224	0.0002	0.0001	0.0002
225	0.0004	0.0003	0.0006
226	0.0008	0.0006	0.0012
227	0.0017	0.0013	0.0024
228	0.0033	0.0025	0.0044
229	0.0059	0.0046	0.0077
230	0.0099	0.0079	0.0128
231	0.0151	0.0121	0.0191
232	0.0225	0.0183	0.0281
233	0.0334	0.0275	0.0411
234	0.0495	0.0413	0.0602
235	0.0735	0.0620	0.0879
236	0.1045	0.0892	0.1235
237	0.1480	0.1276	0.1725

238	0.2075	0.1809	0.2389
239	0.2875	0.2534	0.3271
240	0.3929	0.3497	0.4417
241	0.5179	0.4650	0.5765
242	0.6740	0.6102	0.7431
243	0.8658	0.7900	0.9463
244	1.0981	1.0094	1.1905
245	1.3757	1.2733	1.4802
246	1.6819	1.5660	1.7981
247	2.0356	1.9058	2.1633
248	2.4400	2.2962	2.5788
249	2.8976	2.7399	3.0472
250	3.4105	3.2393	3.5702
251	3.9495	3.7659	4.1183
252	4.5396	4.3442	4.7165
253	5.1802	4.9739	5.3644
254	5.8698	5.6535	6.0601
255	6.6057	6.3806	6.8010
256	7.3486	7.1161	7.5478
257	8.1254	7.8868	8.3276
258	8.9313	8.6878	9.1353
259	9.7607	9.5136	9.9654
260	10.6073	10.3579	10.8118
261	11.4283	11.1778	11.6322
262	12.2509	12.0003	12.4531
263	13.0689	12.8194	13.2690
264	13.8769	13.6293	14.0742
265	14.6698	14.4251	14.8639
266	15.4099	15.1685	15.6006
267	16.1249	15.8876	16.3120
268	16.8130	16.5803	16.9965
269	17.4721	17.2444	17.6517
270	18.0975	17.8752	18.2733
271	18.6566	18.4400	18.8289
272	19.1687	18.9581	19.3375
273	19.6169	19.4126	19.7823
274	19.9797	19.7822	20.1410
275	20.2460	20.0556	20.4036
276	20.3762	20.1932	20.5299
277	20.3990	20.2238	20.5487
278	20.3412	20.1737	20.4859
279	20.2226	20.0629	20.3632
280	20.0877	19.9354	20.2243
281	19.9394	19.7941	20.0725
282	19.7964	19.6578	19.9252
283	19.6433	19.5113	19.7688

284	19.4411	19.3157	19.5631
285	19.1710	19.0525	19.2889
286	18.7767	18.6656	18.8884
287	18.2924	18.1888	18.3980
288	17.6922	17.5965	17.7908
289	17.0296	16.9421	17.1209
290	16.3008	16.2214	16.3834
291	15.5487	15.4770	15.6241
292	14.7899	14.7253	14.8584
293	14.0517	13.9934	14.1141
294	13.3460	13.2929	13.4033
295	12.6822	12.6333	12.7349
296	12.0616	12.0159	12.1113
297	11.4913	11.4478	11.5388
298	10.9660	10.9240	11.0121
299	10.4889	10.4477	10.5341
300	10.0519	10.0109	10.0968
301	9.6504	9.6093	9.6952
302	9.2851	9.2437	9.3301
303	8.9482	8.9063	8.9935
304	8.6385	8.5960	8.6842
305	8.3529	8.3096	8.3989
306	8.0857	8.0418	8.1321
307	7.8368	7.7922	7.8837
308	7.6041	7.5589	7.6514
309	7.3844	7.3386	7.4320
310	7.1765	7.1300	7.2243
311	6.9796	6.9326	7.0278
312	6.7915	6.7441	6.8400
313	6.6114	6.5636	6.6600
314	6.4388	6.3906	6.4876
315	6.2728	6.2244	6.3218
316	6.1125	6.0638	6.1617
317	5.9574	5.9085	6.0066
318	5.8074	5.7584	5.8566
319	5.6621	5.6130	5.7114
320	5.5209	5.4717	5.5702
321	5.3838	5.3346	5.4330
322	5.2504	5.2013	5.2995
323	5.1208	5.0718	5.1698
324	4.9947	4.9458	5.0436
325	4.8718	4.8230	4.9205
326	4.7524	4.7039	4.8009
327	4.6361	4.5878	4.6844
328	4.5229	4.4749	4.5710
329	4.4130	4.3652	4.4608

330	4.3061	4.2586	4.3536
331	4.2026	4.1554	4.2498
332	4.1020	4.0551	4.1489
333	4.0043	3.9578	4.0509
334	3.9096	3.8634	3.9558
335	3.8177	3.7719	3.8636
336	3.7291	3.6836	3.7746
337	3.6435	3.5984	3.6886
338	3.5608	3.5160	3.6054
339	3.4808	3.4364	3.5251
340	3.4037	3.3597	3.4476
341	3.3297	3.2862	3.3732
342	3.2586	3.2154	3.3017
343	3.1903	3.1474	3.2330
344	3.1247	3.0823	3.1671
345	3.0621	3.0200	3.1041
346	3.0027	2.9610	3.0443
347	2.9464	2.9050	2.9876
348	2.8931	2.8520	2.9341
349	2.8431	2.8024	2.8837
350	2.7966	2.7562	2.8369
351	2.7541	2.7140	2.7942
352	2.7155	2.6756	2.7553
353	2.6809	2.6413	2.7205
354	2.6503	2.6110	2.6898
355	2.6236	2.5845	2.6629
356	2.6004	2.5616	2.6397
357	2.5795	2.5410	2.6186
358	2.5591	2.5211	2.5980
359	2.5368	2.4993	2.5756
360	2.5098	2.4730	2.5483
361	2.4750	2.4392	2.5130
362	2.4290	2.3945	2.4664
363	2.3691	2.3361	2.4056
364	2.2937	2.2624	2.3291
365	2.2023	2.1729	2.2364
366	2.0961	2.0687	2.1287
367	1.9771	1.9517	2.0081
368	1.8482	1.8248	1.8775
369	1.7130	1.6914	1.7406
370	1.5738	1.5539	1.5996
371	1.4363	1.4180	1.4604
372	1.3033	1.2864	1.3257
373	1.1769	1.1614	1.1977
374	1.0585	1.0442	1.0777
375	0.9491	0.9359	0.9668

376	0.8490	0.8370	0.8653
377	0.7581	0.7470	0.7731
378	0.6760	0.6659	0.6898
379	0.6026	0.5933	0.6151
380	0.5369	0.5284	0.5483
381	0.4782	0.4704	0.4887
382	0.4259	0.4188	0.4355
383	0.3794	0.3728	0.3880
384	0.3379	0.3320	0.3458
385	0.3011	0.2957	0.3083
386	0.2687	0.2637	0.2752
387	0.2398	0.2353	0.2457
388	0.2142	0.2100	0.2196
389	0.1914	0.1876	0.1963
390	0.1712	0.1677	0.1756
391	0.1533	0.1501	0.1573
392	0.1375	0.1345	0.1411
393	0.1234	0.1207	0.1267
394	0.1108	0.1083	0.1138
395	0.0996	0.0973	0.1023
396	0.0896	0.0875	0.0921
397	0.0808	0.0788	0.0830
398	0.0728	0.0710	0.0749
399	0.0657	0.0640	0.0675
400	0.0593	0.0577	0.0610
401	0.0535	0.0521	0.0551
402	0.0484	0.0471	0.0498
403	0.0437	0.0425	0.0450
404	0.0395	0.0384	0.0407
405	0.0358	0.0347	0.0368
406	0.0323	0.0314	0.0333
407	0.0293	0.0284	0.0301
408	0.0264	0.0257	0.0272
409	0.0239	0.0232	0.0246
410	0.0216	0.0210	0.0223
411	0.0195	0.0189	0.0201
412	0.0177	0.0171	0.0182
413	0.0160	0.0154	0.0164
414	0.0144	0.0139	0.0149
415	0.0130	0.0126	0.0134
416	0.0117	0.0113	0.0121
417	0.0106	0.0102	0.0109
418	0.0095	0.0092	0.0098
419	0.0086	0.0083	0.0089
420	0.0078	0.0075	0.0080
421	0.0070	0.0067	0.0072

422	0.0063	0.0061	0.0065
423	0.0057	0.0054	0.0058
424	0.0051	0.0049	0.0052
425	0.0046	0.0044	0.0047
426	0.0041	0.0039	0.0042
427	0.0037	0.0035	0.0038
428	0.0033	0.0032	0.0034
429	0.0030	0.0028	0.0031
430	0.0027	0.0025	0.0027
431	0.0024	0.0023	0.0025
432	0.0021	0.0020	0.0022
433	0.0019	0.0018	0.0020
434	0.0017	0.0016	0.0018
435	0.0015	0.0015	0.0016
436	0.0014	0.0013	0.0014
437	0.0012	0.0012	0.0013
438	0.0011	0.0010	0.0011
439	0.0010	0.0009	0.0010
440	0.0009	0.0008	0.0009
441	0.0008	0.0007	0.0008
442	0.0007	0.0006	0.0007
443	0.0006	0.0006	0.0006
444	0.0005	0.0005	0.0006
445	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005
446	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004
447	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004
448	0.0003	0.0003	0.0003
449	0.0003	0.0003	0.0003
450	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003
451	0.0002	0.0000	0.0000
452	0.0002	0.0000	0.0000
453	0.0002	0.0000	0.0000
454	0.0002	0.0000	0.0000
455	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000
456	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000
457	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000
458	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000
459	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000
460	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000
461	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000
462	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000
463	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
464	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
465	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
466	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
467	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

468	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
469	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
470	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
471	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
472	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
473	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
474	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
475	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
476	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
477	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
478	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
479	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
480	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
481	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
482	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
483	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
484	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
485	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
486	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
487	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
488	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
489	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
490	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
491	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
492	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
493	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
494	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
495	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
496	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
497	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
498	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
499	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
500	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

3-element S-CALe UP (W44) trap reflectance		Based on standard uncertainty, $k=1$; low limit = nominal refl - standard uncertainty	Based on standard uncertainty, $k=1$; high limit = nominal refl + standard uncertainty
Wavelength (nm)	Nominal reflectance (%)	Low reflectance limit (%)	High reflectance limit (%)
200	8.2940	7.6738	9.0050
201	8.6054	7.9641	9.3417
202	8.7752	8.1190	9.5296
203	8.8229	8.1587	9.5873
204	8.7807	8.1161	9.5467
205	8.6906	8.0327	9.4498
206	8.5974	7.9517	9.3430
207	8.5408	7.9104	9.2685
208	8.5473	7.9323	9.2561
209	8.6255	8.0235	9.3176
210	8.7661	8.1730	9.4456
211	8.9452	8.3567	9.6173
212	9.1302	8.5423	9.7997
213	9.2861	8.6959	9.9569
214	9.3819	8.7876	10.0565
215	9.3935	8.7944	10.0732
216	9.3057	8.7025	9.9903
217	9.1113	8.5055	9.7991
218	8.8102	8.2047	9.4983
219	8.4087	7.8072	9.0929
220	7.9196	7.3270	8.5949
221	7.3586	6.7800	8.0193
222	6.7456	6.1866	7.3853
223	6.1024	5.5688	6.7148
224	5.4488	4.9463	6.0276
225	4.8017	4.3356	5.3407
226	4.1705	3.7461	4.6635
227	3.5678	3.1897	4.0094
228	3.0071	2.6781	3.3934
229	2.5096	2.2297	2.8401
230	2.0970	1.8624	2.3753
231	1.7822	1.5860	2.0156
232	1.5670	1.4006	1.7652
233	1.4437	1.2983	1.6166
234	1.4018	1.2692	1.5586
235	1.4313	1.3046	1.5798
236	1.5233	1.3967	1.6700
237	1.6723	1.5412	1.8226
238	1.8739	1.7347	2.0322
239	2.1238	1.9735	2.2935
240	2.4177	2.2541	2.6016

241	2.7502	2.5715	2.9504
242	3.1162	2.9211	3.3346
243	3.5095	3.2970	3.7472
244	3.9241	3.6933	4.1820
245	4.3539	4.1044	4.6328
246	4.7924	4.5239	5.0927
247	5.2344	4.9468	5.5562
248	5.6763	5.3699	6.0196
249	6.1135	5.7886	6.4777
250	6.5437	6.2011	6.9279
251	6.9670	6.6087	7.3689
252	7.3824	7.0098	7.8005
253	7.7935	7.4077	8.2264
254	8.2026	7.8062	8.6475
255	8.6147	8.2097	9.0691
256	9.0346	8.6233	9.4958
257	9.4682	9.0523	9.9341
258	9.9204	9.5025	10.3880
259	10.3956	9.9775	10.8628
260	10.8954	10.4784	11.3604
261	11.4197	11.0042	11.8819
262	11.9667	11.5537	12.4248
263	12.5308	12.1205	12.9847
264	13.1058	12.6978	13.5555
265	13.6832	13.2765	14.1299
266	14.2532	13.8477	14.6972
267	14.8058	14.4007	15.2480
268	15.3325	14.9268	15.7740
269	15.8236	15.4162	16.2660
270	16.2686	15.8588	16.7124
271	16.6559	16.2430	17.1020
272	16.9725	16.5559	17.4217
273	17.1972	16.7767	17.6498
274	17.3056	16.8812	17.7615
275	17.2858	16.8580	17.7446
276	17.1200	16.6898	17.5811
277	16.8181	16.3866	17.2809
278	16.4103	15.9783	16.8739
279	15.9206	15.4886	16.3844
280	15.3948	14.9633	15.8586
281	14.8521	14.4214	15.3155
282	14.2974	13.8683	14.7594
283	13.7187	13.2921	14.1783
284	13.0843	12.6621	13.5393
285	12.3844	11.9692	12.8323
286	11.5893	11.1848	12.0261

287	10.7300	10.3390	11.1526
288	9.7983	9.4244	10.2030
289	8.8515	8.4973	9.2354
290	7.8987	7.5668	8.2589
291	6.9828	6.6745	7.3182
292	6.1178	5.8338	6.4273
293	5.3234	5.0639	5.6070
294	4.6068	4.3712	4.8649
295	3.9699	3.7574	4.2032
296	3.4111	3.2205	3.6209
297	2.9261	2.7560	3.1140
298	2.5068	2.3558	2.6741
299	2.1486	2.0152	2.2968
300	1.8426	1.7252	1.9734
301	1.5826	1.4798	1.6976
302	1.3636	1.2739	1.4643
303	1.1787	1.1008	1.2663
304	1.0235	0.9562	1.0995
305	0.8943	0.8363	0.9599
306	0.7866	0.7369	0.8431
307	0.6977	0.6553	0.7460
308	0.6249	0.5889	0.6660
309	0.5657	0.5352	0.6006
310	0.5182	0.4925	0.5476
311	0.4808	0.4594	0.5055
312	0.4521	0.4344	0.4726
313	0.4309	0.4163	0.4477
314	0.4162	0.4044	0.4300
315	0.4073	0.3979	0.4184
316	0.4035	0.3960	0.4122
317	0.4043	0.3984	0.4110
318	0.4092	0.4045	0.4144
319	0.4177	0.4139	0.4220
320	0.4297	0.4261	0.4335
321	0.4446	0.4409	0.4485
322	0.4623	0.4582	0.4666
323	0.4825	0.4778	0.4872
324	0.5049	0.4997	0.5101
325	0.5293	0.5236	0.5348
326	0.5554	0.5494	0.5612
327	0.5829	0.5766	0.5889
328	0.6116	0.6052	0.6177
329	0.6416	0.6351	0.6477
330	0.6722	0.6658	0.6783
331	0.7036	0.6973	0.7096
332	0.7356	0.7293	0.7413

333	0.7679	0.7618	0.7736
334	0.8007	0.7946	0.8062
335	0.8337	0.8277	0.8392
336	0.8670	0.8610	0.8726
337	0.9006	0.8944	0.9063
338	0.9347	0.9283	0.9406
339	0.9692	0.9626	0.9755
340	1.0045	0.9976	1.0112
341	1.0406	1.0334	1.0477
342	1.0779	1.0704	1.0854
343	1.1166	1.1087	1.1245
344	1.1571	1.1489	1.1655
345	1.1999	1.1914	1.2084
346	1.2451	1.2364	1.2540
347	1.2936	1.2846	1.3027
348	1.3457	1.3365	1.3551
349	1.4022	1.3928	1.4117
350	1.4638	1.4541	1.4735
351	1.5312	1.5213	1.5412
352	1.6056	1.5953	1.6160
353	1.6881	1.6772	1.6989
354	1.7795	1.7679	1.7910
355	1.8812	1.8686	1.8937
356	1.9941	1.9803	2.0078
357	2.1190	2.1039	2.1342
358	2.2561	2.2392	2.2726
359	2.4044	2.3857	2.4226
360	2.5626	2.5416	2.5825
361	2.7272	2.7039	2.7490
362	2.8938	2.8681	2.9176
363	3.0574	3.0291	3.0833
364	3.2123	3.1813	3.2403
365	3.3531	3.3194	3.3833
366	3.4751	3.4387	3.5075
367	3.5749	3.5360	3.6094
368	3.6503	3.6090	3.6867
369	3.7006	3.6572	3.7386
370	3.7236	3.6785	3.7629
371	3.7250	3.6786	3.7652
372	3.7073	3.6602	3.7480
373	3.6741	3.6266	3.7149
374	3.6279	3.5806	3.6685
375	3.5717	3.5249	3.6117
376	3.5079	3.4619	3.5471
377	3.4383	3.3934	3.4764
378	3.3647	3.3212	3.4015

379	3.2885	3.2465	3.3238
380	3.2108	3.1705	3.2445
381	3.1323	3.0938	3.1644
382	3.0535	3.0169	3.0839
383	2.9748	2.9400	3.0035
384	2.8963	2.8634	2.9233
385	2.8186	2.7876	2.8439
386	2.7423	2.7133	2.7659
387	2.6671	2.6399	2.6891
388	2.5930	2.5676	2.6134
389	2.5202	2.4965	2.5391
390	2.4486	2.4266	2.4661
391	2.3790	2.3586	2.3952
392	2.3113	2.2924	2.3263
393	2.2450	2.2275	2.2588
394	2.1802	2.1638	2.1929
395	2.1167	2.1014	2.1286
396	2.0551	2.0407	2.0661
397	1.9952	1.9817	2.0056
398	1.9365	1.9237	1.9465
399	1.8790	1.8667	1.8887
400	1.8225	1.8106	1.8322
401	1.7678	1.7561	1.7774
402	1.7140	1.7025	1.7238
403	1.6611	1.6496	1.6711
404	1.6090	1.5975	1.6193
405	1.5581	1.5464	1.5686
406	1.5080	1.4962	1.5189
407	1.4586	1.4466	1.4699
408	1.4100	1.3977	1.4216
409	1.3622	1.3497	1.3742
410	1.3152	1.3024	1.3275
411	1.2689	1.2559	1.2815
412	1.2232	1.2100	1.2361
413	1.1785	1.1650	1.1917
414	1.1345	1.1209	1.1479
415	1.0913	1.0775	1.1049
416	1.0489	1.0349	1.0626
417	1.0074	0.9933	1.0213
418	0.9667	0.9525	0.9807
419	0.9267	0.9126	0.9408
420	0.8879	0.8737	0.9020
421	0.8498	0.8357	0.8640
422	0.8127	0.7986	0.8268
423	0.7765	0.7625	0.7906
424	0.7413	0.7274	0.7554

425	0.7071	0.6933	0.7210
426	0.6738	0.6602	0.6876
427	0.6415	0.6281	0.6552
428	0.6102	0.5970	0.6237
429	0.5798	0.5668	0.5931
430	0.5506	0.5378	0.5637
431	0.5223	0.5098	0.5351
432	0.4949	0.4827	0.5075
433	0.4686	0.4567	0.4809
434	0.4433	0.4316	0.4553
435	0.4189	0.4075	0.4306
436	0.3955	0.3845	0.4069
437	0.3730	0.3623	0.3841
438	0.3515	0.3411	0.3622
439	0.3309	0.3208	0.3413
440	0.3111	0.3015	0.3213
441	0.2923	0.2830	0.3021
442	0.2744	0.2654	0.2838
443	0.2573	0.2486	0.2664
444	0.2410	0.2327	0.2498
445	0.2256	0.2176	0.2340
446	0.2109	0.2033	0.2189
447	0.1970	0.1897	0.2047
448	0.1838	0.1769	0.1912
449	0.1714	0.1647	0.1784
450	0.1596	0.1533	0.1663
451	0.1485	0.1425	0.1549
452	0.1380	0.1323	0.1441
453	0.1282	0.1228	0.1339
454	0.1189	0.1138	0.1244
455	0.1102	0.1054	0.1154
456	0.1021	0.0975	0.1070
457	0.0945	0.0902	0.0991
458	0.0873	0.0833	0.0917
459	0.0807	0.0769	0.0847
460	0.0744	0.0709	0.0783
461	0.0686	0.0653	0.0722
462	0.0632	0.0601	0.0666
463	0.0582	0.0553	0.0614
464	0.0536	0.0508	0.0565
465	0.0492	0.0467	0.0520
466	0.0452	0.0429	0.0478
467	0.0415	0.0394	0.0439
468	0.0381	0.0361	0.0403
469	0.0350	0.0331	0.0370
470	0.0320	0.0303	0.0339

471	0.0294	0.0278	0.0311
472	0.0269	0.0254	0.0285
473	0.0246	0.0233	0.0261
474	0.0226	0.0213	0.0239
475	0.0207	0.0195	0.0219
476	0.0189	0.0179	0.0201
477	0.0173	0.0164	0.0184
478	0.0159	0.0150	0.0168
479	0.0146	0.0138	0.0154
480	0.0133	0.0126	0.0141
481	0.0122	0.0116	0.0130
482	0.0112	0.0106	0.0119
483	0.0103	0.0098	0.0109
484	0.0095	0.0090	0.0100
485	0.0088	0.0083	0.0092
486	0.0081	0.0077	0.0085
487	0.0075	0.0071	0.0079
488	0.0069	0.0066	0.0073
489	0.0064	0.0061	0.0067
490	0.0060	0.0057	0.0062
491	0.0056	0.0053	0.0058
492	0.0052	0.0050	0.0054
493	0.0049	0.0047	0.0051
494	0.0046	0.0044	0.0048
495	0.0043	0.0042	0.0045
496	0.0041	0.0040	0.0042
497	0.0039	0.0038	0.0040
498	0.0037	0.0036	0.0038
499	0.0035	0.0035	0.0036
500	0.0034	0.0033	0.0035